

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

D2.5 Assessment of success stories

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Executive Summary

This document is part of the BIORURAL project to support the European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN). It focuses on assessing rural bioeconomy success stories to understand the factors that have contributed to their effectiveness and accomplishment. The highlighted cases, which span five core Bioeconomy themes, exemplify successful transitions from ideas to tangible products.

The work carried out consisted in in-depth exploring the innovation process of selected success stories, and to present them through written and video-based content. The explored success stories can serve as testimonials and good example in the BioRural toolbox.

Furthermore, analysing the several innovation processes, common recurring elements emerge, noteworthy elements allowed for the identification of 6 common and important characteristics to achieve successful business models which can set the basis for development of future success stories. These characteristics are: genuine and friendly biomass management, niche market and value chain alignment, practical and tailor-made solutions, adaptive and sustainable growth strategy, research process and experimental pilots, and collaboration with local stakeholders.

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1 Introduction

One of the key pillars of BIORURAL project is to **establish a European Rural Bioeconomy Network (ERBN)**, allowing neighbouring countries to **connect** and to **stimulate knowledge exchange** in the development of ongoing and emerging rural bioeconomy initiatives. The BIORURAL network is designed to highlight local and regional stakeholders involved in the development of circular and bio-based economy, thereby supporting sustainable local solutions. This document focuses on developing an assessment of specific rural **Bioeconomy success stories** to detect the main factors that led to their success. The outcome of this deliverable is meant to be followed by the continuous identification of other success stories based on similar operational characteristics. Likewise, the investigation of the entrepreneurial journey of the selected success stories presented in this deliverable is meant to serve as a motivational and inspiring basis for EU-wide replication.

The success stories' outcomes will serve as testimonials in the BioRural toolbox and will make it possible to consider the vision of the Biorural project in terms of **examples of rural bioeconomy experiences to follow and to learn from**. As a result, the outcome seeks to raise awareness and share best practice for the introduction of more bio-based innovation in rural areas. Subsequently, it will help to outline criteria for what constitutes a Biorural success story and provide an inspirational framework to encourage the transition toward European rural bioeconomy.

Eight success stories previously identified by the Biorural partnership are presented and examined to determine the success factors of these initiatives. In line with Biorural's multi-stakeholder approach, the analysis of the success stories focusses on the innovation processes. As such, to properly outline the outcomes of the success stories assessment a **common analytical scheme** has been taken into consideration. Thus, the initial design that have been chosen for exploring the success stories innovation processes is addressed to be a joined exploration and learning process of the interested actors building upon participatory methodologies (as in Smart-AKIS, INNOSETA and AgroFossilFree).

Figure 1: The innovation Spiral

The **principle** of the analysis scheme is based on the observation that each stage of the Innovation Spiral includes different **key activities** to be performed, **actors to be involved** and typical **pitfalls** to be avoided. The Innovation Spiral identifies seven stages in an innovation process, from the initial idea until the embedding stage of the innovation. According to Wielinga and Koutsouris (2018) the stages are as follows:

1. **Initial idea:** Someone has an idea in response to a problem or an opportunity. New ideas can also emerge from creative group interaction. Exposure to the world beyond the comfort zone is often a trigger for new initiatives.
2. **Inspiration:** Others become inspired and form a “warm network” around the initiative. These are likeminded people with similar ambitions.
3. **Planning:** The warm network of initiators organises itself, and negotiates space for development with managers and financiers who are in control of the conditions.

4. **Development:** In the relatively safe environment thus created, the initiators develop new practices and evidence of their effectiveness. For doing so, connection is made with relevant experts from experience or/and science.

5. **Realisation:** The new practice is introduced in the world outside the safe pilot area. This usually involves competition or negotiation with stakeholders who are affected by the changes caused by the new practice. Once this practice is widely accepted as being valuable, it can be called an innovation.

6. **Dissemination:** Other people become interested and implement the innovation. This can occur by itself, and it can also be promoted.

7. **Embedding:** The innovation becomes common practice, and structures adapt to the new reality. In this stage, gatekeepers, managers and policymakers who control the structures are the actors involved.

The **ongoing objective** of this success stories assessment is to provide written, and video based content to reinforce the implementation of BIORURAL's actions. Furthermore, the **innovation process assessment** as written, and **video-based content material** is expected to assist the transition context towards **circular Bioeconomy** across Europe at local and regional scale and support innovators to scale-up inclusive and small-scale bio-based solutions in rural areas.

For this purpose, the 8 cases that have successfully been transformed from ideas into products, are covering the **5 Bioeconomy themes:**

- Food and agriculture
- Forestry and natural habitats
- Aquatic systems
- Bioenergy
- Biomaterials

2 Methodology

This section emphasizes the methodology adopted in task 2.3 and aims to provide an overview of the fieldwork carried out. At the heart of the investigation into the innovation processes of success stories, the research is fundamentally qualitative. Grounded on the principle of participatory methodology, the path taken was led by having several regional partners close to the companies and able to exchange directly with the key representatives of each success story.

Figure 2: Success stories - BIORURAL

Therefore, the operational approach involved in the assessment of each success story is based on in-depth and semi-structured interviews. Conducting interviews, also considering the regional know-how of the involved BIORURAL partner, emerged as particularly fitting instruments. Especially to extract underlying experiences and unlocking the mechanisms of decision-making processes such as allowing the interviewee to be fully involved.

Accordingly, the methodology has been developed to frame common understandings and guidelines among all the concerned partners. This led to the set up a specific guideline document (available in annexes). It includes a description of the action, such as step-by-step procedures and schemes to follow for the interview and video to produce.

From the interview result, the identified innovation processes items were outlined, narrowed, analyzed, and reviewed aiming to offer insightful narratives and learnings about the key consideration of each success story.

3 Innovation processes of selected success stories

3.1 Bio-based garden by Delphy – Netherlands

Company profile information

Delphy, stands as a reference in expertise for the food & flowers sectors. Each team within Delphy specializes in specific botanical sectors, offering unparalleled knowledge to its global partners. Emphasizing reliability, responsibility, and independence, Delphy's rich history and its team of experts ensure consistent and unbiased advising services. Globally, Delphy is renowned as a trusted knowledge source for its partners.

The "Biobased Innovations Garden", aim to establish as an epicenter of innovation in the cultivation and application of new green raw materials for industries.

Contact profile information

Cor van Oers is a specialist in project management, biomass, subsidies, and biobased innovations. Holding studies and having background in agriculture, Cor has over decade of experience in the experimental farm and biobased sector. This experience led him to experiment and investigate diverse potential applications within the biobased economy. Cor serves as the Manager of Arable Farming and Field Vegetables, showcasing his dedication to innovation and research in sustainable agriculture and the transition toward a greener economy.

3.1.1 Description of the innovation process

3.1.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial idea

In response to the challenges of carbon reduction, the province of Zeeland, in collaboration with a Research station and Delphy, came up with the idea of the Biobased Innovation Garden. The initiative stemmed from a collective desire to address biobased economy challenges. The primary objective was to establish a field laboratory dedicated to new crops and new applications and looking forward the identification of suitable crops addressing value in bio-based economy. The challenges at the beginning were about understanding growth dynamics, and determining optimal cultivation conditions for innovative solutions that can develop the market for biobased products.

Accordingly, the initial idea of the Biobased Garden was about recognizing valuable crops, cultivating them, refining the production, and laying the groundwork to develop upon biobased products.

Inspiration

The early actors involved in the development were essentially people from the chemical and construction industry, but other contributory items in this moment were the province of Zeeland itself and the "Circular Bio-based Delta" network, which is an organization for startups, new businesses, and related ventures in the Netherlands.

Acting as both as reference and an advisory group, the network played an ongoing role in shaping the garden's direction and how it should look like.

3.1.1.2 Implementation phase

Planning

In 2014, the Bio-based Innovation Garden project was started, aiming to transition from experimental beginnings to a pilot phase and to collaborate with various companies for broader business applications, such as paper or building materials.

Development

Besides, the garden's design was conceptualized to span over one hectare, featuring 64 plots, each measuring 120 square meters. These plots were devised to enable comprehensive biomass research and production. Combined grass lanes ensured the plots and access to researchers allowing a whole observation of selected plant growth.

Realisation

The garden's dual functionality came to the forefront as it began serving both as a research hotspot and a place for networking biomass experimentation. During its evolution, the garden established itself as more than a research space by regularly hosting meetings and catalyzing audience, from farmers to potential end-users such as architects and factories.

It emerged as a vibrant place to do experimental research and for people to meet each other, encouraging collaborations that might not have materialized in traditional settings. This dynamic features of research, networking, and practical applications, personifying the practices behind the Bio-based Innovation Garden.

3.1.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

The foundation for disseminating the activities of the Bio-based Garden is explicitly supported by the development of a network, comprising a diverse individual to keep aware with newsletters and meetings. Still, due to the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the garden's outreach turned to digital approaches like webinars. These webinars spotted a wide range of topics, from nuances of the biobased economy to intricate aspects of construction, coloring, and refining processes. Through these endeavors, the intent is to engage not only the agricultural stakeholders but likewise the potential end users.

Embedding

The garden, though yet to achieve "mainstream" recognition, has carved a niche as an epicenter of bio-sourced innovation. It acts as a bridge between the agricultural domain and sectors like chemicals and construction, catalyzing the new opportunities.

While the Biobased Innovation Garden set on the horizon with building materials and textiles as important points, this commitment to evolution and advancement is mirrored by external entities, most notably the Dutch government and its regulatory program. Their proactive engagement, evident in the form of programs championing the use of bio-based building materials, underscores a broader societal shift. It hints at a future where the innovations stemming from the garden don't remain confined to its boundaries but permeate mainstream practices, fostering a sustainable and eco-conscious character.

3.1.2 Main characteristics

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Delphy innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	- Collective ideation for a field laboratory	- Understanding growth dynamics - To be adapted at the biobased market	- Province of Zeeland - Research Station Delphy

	Inspiration	- Gathering advice and finetune the garden's opportunities	- Involve related stakeholder as advisory group	- Chemical and construction industries - "Circular Bio-based Delta" network
Implementation phase	Planning	- Experimental beginning for business application	- N/A	- Building material companies
	Development	- Garden conceptualization	- Address the biomass optimal production	- N/A
	Realisation	- Establishment of the garden and catalyzing audience	- Bringing dual functionality for research and networking	- Related stakeholders (farmers, end-users, architects and factories...)
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	- Creation of a network (newsletter, meetings and webinar)	- Engage end users (not only agricultural stakeholders)	- Related stakeholders (farmers, end-users, architects and factories...)
	Embedding	- Being a niche for biobased innovation - Commitment to evolution and going mainstream (on-going)	- Bringing together the sectors of agriculture and chemicals/construction - Legislation and broader societal shift	- National government

Table 1: Overview of characteristics – Delphy

3.2 Bioplastics by NaturePlast – France

Company profile information

NaturePlast is a company based in Normandy and specialized in the accompaniment of industrialists who wish to develop products from bioplastic materials. Since 2007, NaturePlast offers a complete accompaniment of the customers' projects, from the birth to the industrial realization, through all the coordination steps. NaturePlast is today a key player in bioplastics with the largest portfolio of bioplastic materials in Europe, whether they are of plant origin and/or biodegradable.

The fields of action of NaturePlast are defined in 4 areas of expertise:

- Distribution of bioplastic raw materials
- Valorisation of co-products
- R &D in Formulation, production and characterisation of bioplastic compounds
- Training and technical and economic studies

NaturePlast's products and services are aimed at stakeholders wishing to be sustainably involved in plastics, whether in terms of their origin or their end-of-life. Its turnover in 2022 is 2.5 M€ with a staff of 15 people divided into R&D, production, sales and administration.

Contact profile information

Guillaume Lebouteiller is a chemical engineer from the National Engineering School of Caen in the field of chemistry and materials, with petrochemistry emphasis. He graduated in 2006 and joined Natureplast soon after.

It was a fortuitous meeting with Thomas Lefevre that brought Guillaume to Natureplast, which led the initiative being business-oriented with regard to the import-export of bioplastics. In this sense, Guillaume came to reinforce the skills of Natureplast with a more technical aspect to accompany and work with transformers or even packaging specialists. When Guillaume joined Natureplast, he was responsible of technical and sales activities. In other words, it was very much a question of ensuring the relationship with customers and suppliers. Today, the team has been strengthened and Guillaume supervises this activity while overseeing collaborative projects.

3.2.1 Description of the innovation process

3.2.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial idea

The initial idea of the NaturePlast project is closely linked to environmental concerns and the needs of the materials industry, especially regarding the end of life of materials. Indeed, around 2005, there was a lot of discussion about how to make less and better plastic. The assumption was that there was a need to provide an alternative to petroleum-based materials, and especially by focussing on biodegradable polymers.

The initial idea was therefore to offer polymers with a lower environmental impact than materials derived from fossil fuels and non-degradable. It was an environmental awareness with a very young market as bioplastic materials were emerging on the market.

The starting point for the initiative was a crossroads between Thomas Lefevre and a researcher from the University of Caen who was working on bioplastics and biodegradation. Together they wanted to create a company having at the heart of the matter the perspective of eliminating waste if it is for example lost in nature. In this case, plastic, which is the most visible waste to the naked eye.

In this sense, the benefit of the idea was to be able to sell plastic pellets, via distribution activity, and to modify the polymers to make them usable by the industrials. The innovative solution planned was to intervene in biomass recovery to offer solutions with a reduced carbon impact. In parallel, the idea was also to be able to adapt a biobased product wherever there is plastic thanks to the custom made (packaging, pen, detach parts, etc.). In other words, the advantage was to offer new and more efficient materials for the environment.

Inspiration

The people who were conceptually and operationally involved in the development of the NaturePlast idea were Thomas Lefevre and Guillaume Lebouteiller, who brought in an investment fund to contract their start-up. However, during the creation of their company, they were also able to access the support of local actors in a friendly and informal way, by benefiting from an office in a transport company. This allowed them to structure their first commercial activity of distribution of bioplastic raw materials.

At the same time, they were able to take advantage of the region's attractiveness by receiving help from the regional development agency for export activities (participation in trade fairs, etc.) and help with recruitment and innovation from a public investment bank. In addition, they will seek to be validated by the technical centres and to subscribe to the competitiveness cluster network.

The stakeholders who gravitated around Natureplast in the initial phase allowed them to meet suppliers (who were in Asian countries), to approach prospects and to move forward in order to validate the feasibility of their proposals by developing a technical-commercial proposal and in particular a technical sheet.

3.2.1.2 Implementation phase

Planning

The preparation of the NaturePlast implementation strategy took place at the same time as the start of the commercial activity (distribution of bioplastics) of NaturePlast, namely during the first 3 years of existence and whose objective was to be as independent as possible.

This way, cooperation with the technical centres were of great relevance, enabling them to bring the skills, knowledge and professionalism to carry out R&D projects in-house. In fact, it was a question of having the methodological approach and making aware of the temporal, technical and material aspects that this requires. This is the preliminary work that subsequently enabled them to start working in development (tailor-made materials) to best meet the expectations of industrial and customers and more particularly to verify the economic relevance and know-how to be considered.

In addition, the plastics market is not necessarily oriented towards innovation. So, there was an established routine of the plastics market, an economic reluctance and lack of awareness toward biobased solution. The market was not mature at all and therefore there was no tangible positive economic impact for industrials, which is a first obstacle. One of the first challenges was therefore to very quickly be able to evaluate the performance and the means of manufacture of the materials. Allowing to determine the profitability and the feasibility of envisaged biobased solution. Moreover, as the products were not well known, it was essential to communicate on this subject. The goal was to stand out from the classical production roots by positioning themselves on companies that already had an environmental approach.

The other barrier to overcome was that of the origin of the materials which came mainly from abroad and especially from Asian countries, but this could only be considered in the long term.

Development

NaturePlast's first step towards a biobased innovation and sustainable business was taken in 2009 when it was recognised by the Ministry of Work as a training organisation for the bioplastics market for both plastics manufacturers and end users. By building on their know-how and communication needs, they have developed a range of services (training, market studies, benchmarking, equipment demonstrations, etc.) that allow them to address the issue of bioplastics in a broad and detailed manner.

The traction and progressing of activities were done in 2010 with the creation of a subsidiary R&D entity. This subsidiary entity of NaturePlast, named Biopolynov, marks a major change in their development since this will allow them to propose internally the development of tailor-made materials with short response times. Having the possibility to propose versatile solution adapted to the customer needs was a tipping point towards the current situation of NaturePlast, knowing that before the activity was mainly focused on the commercial distribution of bioplastics.

In-house research and development made it possible to gain autonomy and to submit technical data proposition which brought NaturePlast to implement their solution in the plastic packaging sector. As a matter of principle, this has required to ramp up by recruiting dedicated staff and investing in adapted equipment and machinery.

It can be noted that this step involved the creation of new professions, namely the development of raw materials and making it sustainable and operational for customers.

Moreover, in 2012 by being accompanied by the regional clusters they were able to integrate collaborative project (example: [AGROBOOST](#)) which allowed them to have a wider network, knowledge and experience. This has acted as a springboard within a small or medium size company with a business model not yet perfectly established, allowing to keep jobs and progress in R&D. This had a snowball effect by continuing this effort through the integration of European projects in particular allowing to collaborate with universities and other specialized centre.

Participation in collaborative projects have never stopped since and is notably part of their corporate DNA, allowing them to have visibility and to sustain R&D activity.

By the way, it is also during 2012 that the choice was made to gradually replace, where possible, polymer coming from Asian countries and to work in a more locally and circularly oriented way. Therefore, to progressively limit the paradox with the environmental approach, NaturePlast has initiated its work to valorise local co-products (linked to the production of lynx, to the fishing activity, etc.).

Realisation

The value proposition of NaturePlast is characterized from the moment they have diversified their work thanks to R&D and more particularly in 2014/2015. Indeed, after several years of internal research they have developed a range of materials; a range of polymers with improved thermal resistance that it distributes since.

From this realization, there is a recognition of their expertise, and we see a commercialization start of in-house research and customers coming to search for them rather than the reverse. In a similar way, in 2017 and 2018, NaturePlast is increasingly being brought to bear witness of their journey and innovation.

3.2.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

From 2015, the global offer has been framed with a diffusion of biobased products and an increase in the sale of materials for export. The diffusion of the solutions was partly done thanks to the European collaborative project that allowed NaturePlast to make a name for itself in bioplastic, by building a website allowing them to be better identified and by participating in major trade fairs such as the FIP event in France or the K and Interpack event in Germany.

In the same year, 2015, the synergies are aligned for NaturePlast as we see an evolution of the plastic legislation such as for cutlery or cotton buds which generates the consequence of having several materials to replace and which gives the trend to come at the industry. This will indirectly promote NaturePlast's solutions on the market, which is starting to open up. In continuity, in the years 2018/2019, we observe a change of mentality among citizens (plastic bashing) which accelerates the demand and brings bioplastics as a topic of conversation more and more preponderant.

At the industry level, the covid puts a break but also made the perception of biosolutions evolve with an explosion of demand and a return of industrialists who relaunch this subject. The post-covid changeover of industrialists in relation to product dependency has highlighted the need to work with local products.

In other words, the dissemination on the market was done naturally since when the civil society and the industrialists were ready to adopt biobased processes, NaturePlast had well prepared its value proposition and its positioning.

Embedding

To make NaturePlast innovation mainstream, it was first necessary to understand that biobased materials are between 50 and 200% more expensive than petroleum-based materials, and that it is therefore essential to add functionality to the materials such as biodegradability or a specific resistance, besides the valorisation of co-products that can also compensate for the extra cost.

In 2022, NaturePlast counts around 300 customers from all sectors such as packaging, transport, sports, clothing, construction, agriculture. However, it is the marketer of the product who comes to NaturePlast and less often the producer. Today it is difficult to speak of a generalization of the solution because bioplastics are still a niche market, knowing that at the level of the world capacity of polymer plastic the production represents between 1 and 1,5 %.

The main obstacles in the marketing besides the cost of production are the regulatory changes and the implementation of certain techniques. Nevertheless, expert projections indicate that production capacity will triple in the next few years, so the road to adoption of the solution on a large scale is not yet complete, it is only the beginning of a new biobased targeted market.

In this sense, luxury goods and cosmetics are nowadays very demanding sectors as they are able to absorb the extra costs and differentiate themselves essentially by promoting an image that can quickly meet societal expectations. Finally, the integration of bioplastics is very much linked to the aspiration of civil society and by the legislation that by prohibition or authorisation brings the possibilities of this market.

3.2.2 Timeline

Figure 3: Timeline – NaturePlast

3.2.3 Main characteristics

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the NaturePlast innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Early involvement in the issue of eliminating waste and assumptions toward more efficient materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduction in the very young market of biomaterials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University professor
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contract the start-up and - First steps and distribution of bioplastics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To begin commercial activities - Receiving support from the regional ecosystem (e.g., export activities and recruitment) - Developing technical-commercial proposal and technical sheet. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Investment fund - Transport company - Regional development agency - External suppliers - Technical centres - Cluster networks
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design of the company strategy - Becoming independent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Looking to carry out R&D projects in-house (ensuring temporal, technical, and material aspect to be considered) - Business model, feasibility, and economic relevance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical centres
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Become a training organisation for bioplastics and development of services (training, market studies, benchmarking, equipment demonstrations, etc.) - Creation of a subsidiary R&D entity - Integration of collaborative project and European projects - Performing more locally and circular (with local co-products) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Not well-known activity and communication needs - Addressing the issue of bioplastics from a transversal approach - Propose internally the development of tailor-made materials with short response times. - To be able to adapt the customer need. - Recruiting staff and investing in machinery - Brought wider network, knowledge and experience. - Allowing to keep jobs and progress in R&D - Replacement (when possible) the material coming from Asian countries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beneficiaries of the services (plastics manufacturers and end users) - Regional clusters, universities and other specialized centre - Ministry of Work
	Reali satio	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishment of an improved range of polymers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Commercialization of in-house research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - N/A

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognition of expertise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frequently requested to testify their experience and customers coming to them directly 	
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building a website and participating in major trade fairs - Evolution of the plastic legislation, “plastic bashing” and Covid 19 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To be better identified and increase sale of material. - To change of mentality among citizens and industrials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - European collaborative project
	Embedding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being a niche market - Going mainstream (on-going) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is essential to add functionality to the materials. - Regulatory changes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 300 customers from all sectors such as packaging, transport, sports, clothing, construction, agriculture (mostly marketer, not producer)

Table 2: Overview of characteristics - NaturePlast

3.3 Sustainable local aquaculture by Pustelnia – Poland

Company profile information

Pustelnia is a family business that breeds fish and sells them. Pustelnia has a Fish Welfare Certificate and is audited every year to obtain the Code of Good Fishing Practice Certificate. The farms carry two main species: common carp and rainbow trout. Carp production in this area dates back to 1760 and the production trout has been developing alongside for the last 20 years. PUSTELNIA faced two main problems: it is located far from retail market (large retailers, processing plants) and the retail market, especially of carp, is unpredictable (extremely changeable prices, seasonal sale). The principle is to produce local, stable and all year-round market.

Pustelnia currently has 28 full-time employees. When the Owner took over the business in 2016, there were 11 people employed in the farm (on breeding). The breeding has not changed very significantly. 3 people have been added to the team: two ichthyologists and 1 additional person were hired as support. As the restaurant was no longer leased out, 11 new people were hired. The office of 1 person (the owner) became 3 people over time. In addition, there are 2 salesmen employed in the store and 3 salesmen operating fish trucks. A total of 28 people. The online store is operated by the administration office.

Contact profile information

Anna Pyć is a graduate of the University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, in 2003 she received a Master's degree in Fisheries. After graduation, she started working for the Headquarters of the Restructuring Agency. It was an important moment for Poland due to preparations for joining the EU. She participated in the preparation process for gaining EU Funds in the field of Fisheries.

The next step was to work for WWF in a project on Baltic fisheries. She later continued as Marketing Manager for Aller Aqua (Sep 2005 - Jun 2017). The last four years of work for Aller Aqua were performed remotely from the Pustelnia. At the moment, Anna is also Vice president of Polish Trout Breeders Association - PTBA, dealing with

international affairs on behalf of the Polish association. For the last two years, she has been on the board of the Federation of European Aquaculture Producers, an organization that brings together national organizations. On her behalf, she participates in Consultations with the European Commission on many issues and is a member of Aquaculture Advisory Council.

3.3.1 Description of the innovation process

3.3.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial idea

The initial idea to develop the fish farm and restaurant appeared in 1980s and thanks to the hard work of Mr and Mrs Pyć (Anna's parents) was successfully realised until 2016, when Anna and her husband Sebastian took over the farm's management. The first barrier they encountered in the first year of work was a significant decrease in fish production due to conditions unfavourable conditions for fish growth. Due to lower volume of fish, sales had to be retail rather than wholesale (at a lower price). The existing sales model was unsustainable for the upcoming year, so they needed to adjust their current sales model. Organizational changes were made and in the small processing plant, where 20-30 tons were processed in past years, they decided to start processing 80 tons. They increased the processing capacity of their small plant, a decision that proved effective and ensured the company's operations for another year. Besides operational needs, there was also a challenge to change people's mentality to a different way of thinking and working.

Additionally, they had to navigate the administrative and legislative landscape which is invariably a big challenge for the owners. Fish farming is based on a single document - a water-legal permit, which is valid only for 10 years and afterwards must be renewed. Awareness that after 10 years the permit may not be granted makes people reluctant to make large expensive investments. Fish farming's non-priority status in water management, enable the appearance of a new user being more of a priority causes the possibility of not getting a permit. Cooperation between users on the watercourse is essential but is not officially regulated and depends in practice on the good will of people.

Furthermore, protected species of animal became a huge problem for the fish farm as they limit fish production. While the damage caused by beavers is dealt with by workers on an ongoing basis, the impact of the cormorant is much more damaging. The losses are enormous, and the challenge is a matter of scale of fishponds. During winter, three locations (50 hectares) must be protected. Fishermen's main activity currently is to keep an eye on these locations and scare birds (e.g., by using firecrackers or by swimming up to the birds). Among these issues, the idea of utilizing drones to scare away cormorants emerged.

Inspiration

The originators of any changes are mainly Ms. Anna and Mr. Sebastian. Mrs. Anna on the sales, marketing, and administrative side. Mr. Sebastian is more active in terms of technological, technical, and breeding service. In addition, Anna's father who have run the farm since 1974 was also able and willing to advise especially on carp breeding.

Still, within the development of the idea and willingness to work in Pustelnia was born following graduation of Ms. Anna. Before returning home, Anna had the opportunity to work in international teams, both in the government administration, later working in WWF on scientific projects, as well as gaining great managerial skills while working in developing Aller Aqua company. Extensive knowledge and experience in entrepreneurship skills allowed her to obtain EU funds, which significantly helped to create an innovative modern company.

3.3.1.2 Implementation phase: planning, development, and realisation

Planning

The planning for investment began even before the decision to relocate back home, with reduced scope for previous professional activities. Although, the preparation really started at the return home.

The planning process was collaborative. Anna, her husband, and her father jointly discussed and delineated roles for each of them. They talked with friends in search of insights. Their plan was to transition from the wholesale fish market to a stable local market. Specifically, their goal was to develop the market for fresh aquaculture fish within the region, by being trustworthy and long-term label. A key part of the business preparation was to educate local chefs, an initiative they started 20 years ago. Nowadays the trend to use local products is bringing additional new light on the issue.

Development

In 2016, Pustelnia moves to bring their produce closer to consumers, they invest and build a restaurant and a fish shop situated 1 km away from the fish farm. That would be supplied several times a day by the processing plant and would be more accessible for consumers on an everyday basis.

To ensure that their development was rooted in best practices, they sought being in constant contact with experts. Such as Dr. Andrzej Lirski from the Polish Fisheries Institute in Olsztyn regarding market and production planning. Their relationship with the Polish Veterinary Institute in Puławy proved beneficial regarding fish diseases to better prevent and react to these problems. Friends who run restaurants were a lot of support and advice. Each problem was discussed with many people with experience in a given field. As investors, open to talks and sought support. The development phase core challenges to overcome are seasonal production and the unstable market of fish in wholesale.

Moreover, the underdeveloped local fish aquaculture providing processed fish, matching the consumer needs posed further obstacles. To overcome these barriers, they decided to open their restaurant as a platform to showcase and present their products. Part of their development was funded by the EU, the reconstruction of the building in which the restaurant is located, which came with its set of stipulations, such as the procedure for selecting contractors. Many shortcomings of the construction surfaced during the project, but thanks to a good contractor, they managed to overcome all of them.

Realisation

In understanding the innovation at the fish farm, it's crucial to see it as a unified system instead of isolated elements. Traditionally, fish farm involved just people in breeding and farming fish, sometimes sales managers. The Pustelnia fish farm has metamorphosed into a multi-dimensional entity. While fish farming remains foundational, it is complemented by a processing plant, restaurants, shops, and a comprehensive administrative wing. Each element of this structure is interconnected, necessitating intricate coordination, a system that took years to refine and perfect.

Examining the breeding component, carp breeding maintained its quality and quantity consistency. On the other hand, trout farming is being developed, as this fish is very demanding. Given the challenges, especially due to climate change, innovative solutions like efficient water usage and cooling techniques are paramount and remain areas of active development.

Another step of achievement is the processing plant, which has been in operation for about 30 years. However, due to the desire to constantly improve standards and working conditions, it requires expansion and introduction of new innovative devices. Fish from the processing plant is delivered to about 100 contractors (shops, restaurants) within a radius of 100 km from the Pustelnia fish farm. With existing plans and permits, the intention is to pursue facility upgrades.

The restaurant serves a dual purpose: it's both a culinary destination and a symbolic representation of the farm's excellence. The restaurant has employed an outstanding chef who takes care of the team through numerous trainings and adapting to new conditions. At the time of the Covid pandemic in 2020, the entire team was reorganized and engaged in the production of processed fish that could be sold outside. Thanks to this action, the restaurant maintained a constant number of employees and was able to survive this difficult period for gastronomy. At that time, the work of FishTruck was initiated, which are refrigerated trucks used to sell both raw fish and fish

products in the surrounding cities. These refrigerated trucks, serving to multiple cities within a 100 km radius, including Lublin, Sandomierz, Puławy, Lipsk, Ostrowiec Świętokrzyski, Naęczów among many other.

Make the most of on the growing affinity for Pustelnia's fish products, the next step was launching an online store. This platform facilitates fish purchases and delivery across Poland, further expanding the farm's reach and influence.

3.3.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

Promotion and dissemination are components of Pustelnia's approach. Presently, the company maintains an active presence on social media, particularly Facebook. The website serves its purpose but as acknowledged by the owner, there's room for optimization. However, when it comes to launching a comprehensive promotional campaign, the company stands evaluating whether there is a need to make such steps. For the owners, the emphasis is clear: product quality is key. The aim isn't to enlarge the breeding, but to sell 100% of the breeding locally. While efforts to boost sales at physical locations, like the store and restaurant, as well as through FishTrucks, are ongoing, there's still a concentrated measures to strengthen contact with local restaurants. This involves seeking an internal representative dedicated to presenting the product range and establish new cooperation with restaurants.

The company does not have a professionally written communications strategy. Despite this fact, for the past year or so, it has been consciously building a calendar of pre-emptive events in which they should participate or organize. The calendar includes the most important events in the field of breeding, restaurant management, or sales, offering a structured approach to engagement and outreach. The company employs an active restaurant manager who is partly responsible for social media. However, given the extent of communication tasks, mastering them all remains a demanding effort.

Embedding

The number of customers per year is difficult to estimate, as is the number of events organized. The group of regular customers includes about 100 recipients (restaurants, shops) where fresh fish is delivered after initial processing. There is a large group of individual customers using both the restaurant, stationary store, FishTruck as well as the newly opened online store. In addition to individual customer service, the restaurant organizes various types of larger meetings for organized groups, these can be both larger dinners or family meetings such as communion, wedding, or other types of celebrations, but also business meetings, workshops or smaller conferences. The main aim of the company is the production of a high-quality product and its local sale.

The company has development plans and tries to implement them. Mainly through the creation of new products to be sold in their points of sale. The chef of the restaurant constantly introduces new products, not only for use in the restaurant, but also in external stores run by the Pustelnia. Discussions and development work are underway to expand the processing plant, with the purchase of more fish processing equipment. In addition, the company is constantly developing and wants to expand its offer. One of the goals is to open the ponds to visitors. The possibility of creating an accommodation base is also being examined, but one in nature, such as tree houses near the ponds - with the possibility of providing breakfast in a basket. This idea was hindered by the COVID-19 pandemic and currently by inflation (high prices).

3.3.2 Timeline

Figure 4: Timeline – Pustelnia

3.3.3 Main characteristics

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Pustelnia innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Necessity to change the business Model (sales were to be retail rather than wholesale) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decrease in fish production and sales became unsustainable - Upgrade of the small processing plant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Watercourse users - Fishermen's

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Necessity to navigate the administrative landscape to keep water-legal permit and the limitation of fish production due to protected species - Change people's mentality 	
	Inspira tion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisational assignment between project initiators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Internal management attribution and experience in entrepreneurship 	- N/A
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design of the company strategy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Address the market for fresh aquaculture fish in the region by being trustworthy and long-term label - Educate restaurants 	- Local chefs
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building of the restaurant and fish shop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allow access for consumers on an everyday basis - Ensure best practices with experts (market, production, diseases...) - Part of their development was funded European Union (it includes stipulations and procedures) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polish Fisheries Institute - Polish Veterinary Institute - Friends who run restaurants - Construction contractor
	Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Become a multi-dimensional entity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It as a unified system (including fish farming processing plant, restaurants, shops, and a comprehensive administrative wing), all within a 100 km radius - Required expansion and uses of new devices - Looking for efficient water usage - Fish from the processing plant is delivered to about 100 contractors - Refrigerated FishTrucks are initiated in surrounding cities - Online store is launch 	- Contactors (restaurant and shops)
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Balanced marketing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involvement in regular events and social media - To sell firstly 100% of the breeding locally through the shops, restaurant, FishTrucks and online store. - To strengthen and dedicate staff to establish new cooperation with restaurants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restaurant manager (partly responsible for social media) - Internal partnership representative
	Embedd ing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regular customers where fresh fish is delivered after initial processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Various types of meetings are organised such as communion, wedding, celebrations, 	- N/A

			business meetings, workshops or smaller conferences	
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Table 3: Overview of characteristics - Pustelnia

3.4 Latvia’s State Forest by LVM – Latvia

Company profile information

The inception of the Joint Stock Company “Latvia’s State Forests” (LVM) dates back to October 1999, with operations starting in the year 2000. The primary focus of this enterprise is on forestry, the principal revenue stream for the company. Besides forestry, the company has diversified its services to encompass hunting, recreation, producing selected seeds and seedlings, and marketing subsoil resources like sand, gravel, and peat.

Latvian State Forests is a leading forestry company. The organisation embraces technological innovation, deploying planting robots with GPS capabilities, utilizing drones for forest planning, and leveraging the LVM GEO geographical information system for optimized planning and decision-making. Sustainability is at the forefront of their operations, evidenced by their research into carbon sequestration, commitment to a circular economy, and their CO2 neutral status.

It is governed by a council and board representing the primary shareholder, Latvia's Ministry of Agriculture, LVM reported a 2021 turnover of €405.3 million, reflecting a significant increase from the previous years. Compared to 2020, it has increased by €55.6 million.

Contact profile information

Līga Abizāre is the Head of Environmental Education of Latvian State Forests. With nearly 20 years of experience at the organization, her background extends to associations like the World Wide Fund for Nature and the Latvian Environmental Protection Club. She is also the vice-president of the European Forest Pedagogy Organization, which operates under the auspices of ANNO, bringing together forest educators from across Europe. In her previous roles, she played a part in a sustainable forest management campaign focused on the introduction of certification in Latvia, during which a national standard was developed that is still being refined.

Līga joined the Latvian State Forests due to her involvement in the international environmental education program called "Learning about forests" during her tenure at the Latvian Environmental Protection Club. At Latvian State Forests, her role predominantly revolves around bioeconomy. She organizes the Latvia State Forest Bioeconomy School, an annual scholarship contest, taking the young participants on bioeconomy expeditions in partnership with "Silava" and "Latvijas Finieris". Additionally, she oversees projects where youths produce video content for International Forest Day, promoting the significance of bioeconomy in Latvia's economic structure.

3.4.1 Written description of the innovation process

3.4.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial Idea

In response to the problem of workforce availability in the forest planting and restoration sector, the Latvian State Forests introduced the opportunity of using planting robots. These robots were meant to enhance efficiency in planting, but they also to allow to mark each seedling with GPS for improved forest management. However, the innovation brings challenges, including the continuous improvement and maintenance of technology, as well as finding employees skilled in forestry knowledge the integration of technology in forest management is emerging.

Accompanying this, there is an observed issue regarding the protection of young trees from forest animals. Each year, the damages occur across 6,000 – 7,000 hectares. The concern is significant, if young trees are damaged, especially by excessive animal populations, the risk of them dying escalates. This can lead to potential costs of up to two thousand euros per hectare. Potential solutions to protect plantations from adverse weather and animal damage are being considered, though options like fencing or involve more hunting to manage animal populations.

In line with environmental consideration, the efficiency drives every facet of the company's operations. All aspects are considered and evaluated to improve sustainable development. Behind the search for an innovative solution is a means that address operational forest management improvements.

Inspiration

The journey of the Latvian State Forests is punctuated by consistent innovation, each aiming at problem-solving or advancing their operational efficiency. From the introduction of drones that have reshaped forest planning and surveillance, saving substantial time, to the implementation of a geographic information system designed to enhance planning and decision-making processes, the company has brought technology into its operations. Indeed, the company has a separate development part, which develops projects related to innovations and contracts with universities. Collaborations with universities bolster their research endeavors, and the company's vision isn't just restricted to immediate business-centric innovations. They also focus on nurturing future-forward innovations, be it through the support of scientific research, exploration of cutting-edge technologies, or even the potential establishment of new industrial sectors within Latvia.

Moreover, LVM actively participates in cross-border learning, benefiting knowledge exchange from neighboring nations like Poland, Finland or Sweden and in turn, these countries have gained knowledge from LVM about their unique seedling processing methods. This involves treating young trees with protective substances to discourage animals from eating them. As well, LVM has been inspired to experiment using sheep's wool as an eco-friendly protective measure for young trees against forest animals.

3.4.1.2 Implementation phase

Planning

Back in 2011, during a collaborative research project with the Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava", an experiment assessing the efficacy of various trunk protection measures revealed that protective spirals were the most effective. Initially introduced in limited quantities, the deployment of these plastic spirals on tree trunks increased over time. However, the spirals posed environmental challenges: they had to be manually removed from the trees and didn't break down naturally within a desirable timeframe. Given the labor intensity of installing and removing them, their environmental impact, and the disposal costs, LVM planned alternatives.

The planning phase was marked by research, experimentation, and collaboration. The company forged links with universities and looked upon external expertise to drive their innovative attempts. Collaboration was further extended when the Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies conducted interviews with representatives from Latvian State Forests. The goal was to gain deeper insights into the company's methods of young tree protection and inspire other foresters to consider a wider range of alternatives.

Development

This situation necessitated the exploration of alternative protection methods suitable for damp conditions. It was during this period that sheep wool's potential was recognized, initially tested on seedlings up to 3 years old. The wool not only provided a solution to the weather-related issue but also introduced a more environmentally friendly protective measure.

One of the innovative solutions developed was the application of sheep wool on young trees. The wool, wrapped around the trunk, served as a mechanical barrier preventing animals, particularly deer. While initial testing with sheep wool showed promise, the process was tedious, demanding manual stretching, rolling, and winding of the

wool. Recognizing the labor-intensive nature of this method, collaboration with the company "Biolana", which specializes in sheep offal processing and sheep fat-based fertilizer production, was initiated. The objective was to refine the process and develop a finished product that streamline the application in forestry, making it more efficient and user-friendly.

Realization

The realization of the innovation came together of Latvian State Forests and the "Biolana" company in a symbiotic relationship. Here, Latvian State Forests represented the demand side, eager to utilize a product to protect their trees, while "Biolana" embodied the supply side, providing this very product.

For sheep farmers, sheared wool often ended up as waste. "Biolana" took on the challenge of recycling this wool, transforming it into a product that aligned with the requirements of Latvian State Forests. A central challenge lay in the specific characteristics of the wool desired: it needed to retain its natural smell, preventing forest animals, yet it had to be presented in a convenient form that could easily deploy in the forests by manual application. Sheep farmers, seeing the interest in using wool for forest protection, recognized an opportunity to monetize what was formerly waste.

Latvian State Forests assumed the role of a demand generator, outlining specific requirements and encouraging solution providers, primarily small businesses, to address them. This demand acted as a novel approach, including sheep farmers to apply new biobased solution. However, they acknowledged that the current scheme of the innovation was yet to premature for broader market adoption. It wasn't at a stage where private forest owners could easily implement it. Efforts to refine and improve the wool for forestry applications were ongoing, marking the early stages of this innovative undertaking.

3.4.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

Understanding the broader implications of their work, LVM prioritized sharing their findings and methods, not just within their immediate ecosystem but also with the global forestry community. Furthermore, the company's website became a repository of their research, especially studies related to carbon sequestration and CO2 emissions reduction strategies. This transparent sharing positioned LVM in sustainable forestry, providing valuable resources for industry peers and the public alike.

Embedding

The commitment of Latvian State Forests (LVM) to innovation is apparent not just in their attempts but also in their relationships. Collaborations with academic institutions, like the Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava", is very much in place and surrounding the innovative practices they pioneered. These partnerships facilitated a deep dive into research, keeping LVM at new forestry practices.

Many of their experimental projects, are pilot projects searching to become standard practices. This way, ultrasonic devices to shield plants from animal are also being tested by LVM for their efficacy. The appeal of such devices lay in their potential efficiency. If these devices proved effective, they could revolutionize tree protection in the region. Instead of individually treating numerous trees with methods like sheep's wool.

As pioneers, LVM's exploration of these ultrasonic devices had the potential to set a precedent for other forest owners in Latvia. Yet, the verdict on the ultrasonic devices in the context of Latvian conditions remained inconclusive. LVM was in anticipation means, waiting to gather substantial data to form a comprehensive assessment of product's effectiveness.

3.4.2 Data analysis and characteristics

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Algen innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observation concerning the protection of young trees against forest animals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increased risk of death of young trees and monetary cost. - Search for innovations focused on the environment and forest management (rather than options such as fencing or hunting). 	- N/A
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cross-border learning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beneficiary of a shared idea to experiment the use of sheep's wool as an ecological protection 	- Universities and innovation projects (with countries such as Poland, Finland or Sweden)
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifying alternatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The actual plastic solution to protect tree causes environmental issues and labor intensity - Research and collaboration (external expertise) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava" - The Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial testing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sheep wool's potential is recognized and primarily experiment. - Necessity to refine the process and develop a finished product to make it user-friendly 	- Biolona (specializes in sheep offal processing and sheep fat-based fertilizer production)
	Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Symbiotic relationship 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The demand side, eager to utilize a product to protect their trees, while "Biolana" embodied the supply side, providing this product - Although, specific characteristics for the wool is desired 	- Biolona
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sharing forestry community, peers and the public alike 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include the repository of their research, especially in studies related to carbon sequestration and CO2 emissions reduction strategies 	- N/A

Embedding	- Pursue experimental projects and pilot searching to become standard practices	- Build partnership to facilitate deep dive into research	- Latvian State Forest Research Institute “Silava”
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Table 4: Overview of characteristics - LVM

3.5 Olive pomace gasification by Aceites Guadalentin & Bioliza – Spain

This success story shows how the innovations in rural bioeconomy may take place only when two singular pioneering innovators meet, and then the new bioeconomic circular approach materialises.

In this case the two protagonists are:

- Aceites Guadalentin: an olive oil producer, which during the 90s started to look for alternatives to manage the olive pomace (mass of flesh, peeling and bones remaining after extracting olive oil from olives). This company experienced troubles and significant costs to manage this by-product, specially given their remoteness location in rural area of the Jaén province. Their path in the search for alternatives lead the company to test and adopt some partial innovations, till 2017, when they met BIOLIZA.
- BIOLIZA, a knowledge-based start-up of the University of Jaén, born on 2014, and devoted to the application of gasification technologies in the industry. They established as a procurer of the technological solution of gasification, to assist industries in the valorisation of their by-products to obtain energy and biochar.

It is 2017 when these two innovators have the first contact, and start collaborating to trigger the, up to the moment, first olive pomace gasification plant in the olive oil sector, and located in a rural remote area of Jaén (Andalusia, Spain).

Aceites Guadalentin

Company profile information #1 Aceites Guadalentin

Aceites Guadalentin SL is a family business for more than 100 years in the world of olive oil industry in Andalusia olive mill in South Spain. The family is entirely dedicated to the production of the best olive oil and to share knowledge on the olive oil culture. Today, the company proudly showcase its products in many international markets.

After the establishment of the Company in 1926 it has grown and has been adapted to the use of the most modern technology to improve the quality of its olive oil.

It is established in Pozo Alcón, in the province of Jaén, with the largest Surface of olive groves in Spain. It is located in a remote rural area, nearby mountain chains and a natural park, making its access more difficult.

Contact profile information #1 Aceites Guadalentin

Virgilio Gámez is a geologist graduated in 1981 by the University of Granada. After finishing his university studies, he began to look for a place to settle down. His family had a family business, a small oil mill. It had been run by his father and several family members. Since he liked life in the village and decided to stay and take over the reins of the family business.

He shares initially the management with a family member until 1984, and it is from then on when Virgilio begins to act as manager of the business.

Bioliza

Company profile information #2 Bioliza

BIOLIZA is a start-up consultancy of the University of Jaén, created by José Antonio La Cal in 2014 with the aim of serving as an instrument to provide consultancy, especially in the field of olive oil industry by products and its utilisation in industrial applications.

Contact profile information #2 Bioliza

José Antonio La Cal is Industrial Engineer (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 1994), Executive MBA (ESIC, 2011) and PhD from the University of Jaén (2013). He is currently Associate Professor at the University of Jaén since 2005 and teaches biomass/bioenergy at other universities in Spain and South America.

He has been working in the biomass/bioenergy sector for more than 20 years in different fields: technical, managerial, academic, etc. He started as a technician in the Diputación de Jaén (Government of the Jaen province) to advise on business initiatives and training until 2000. From 2000 to 2004 he worked as head of biomass in the Regional Energy Agency of Castilla-La Mancha (AGECAM), and from 2004 to 2012 he was Managing Director of the Energy Management Agency of the Province of Jaén (AGENER). Since 2014, when he founded BIOLIZA, he combines his activity as a consultant with teaching in multiple courses, as well as in the management of some of them, and he keeps a position as associate professor at the University of Jaén.

María Isabel Cano-Caballero Ramírez is Graduate in Law from the University of Granada (1994/1999). Master in "Social Economy and Territorial Development" from the Universities of Jaén and Bordeaux IV (Montesquieu-France) Edition 2006/2007. Her final master's thesis was on "innovation as a driver of local development." She has participated in multiple courses on R&D projects and instruments, technology transfer, industrial property, innovation as a factor of competitiveness, entrepreneurs and Corporate Social Responsibility.

She collaborated as an advisor to the vice-presidency of the Andalusian Association of Technology-Based Companies, being manager of the Technology-Based Company (EBT) Energygem (Biot Group) of the University of Granada. She was also manager of the ItVirtual Consulting Firm (Marwen Calsan Group) providing business advisory services, innovation and Corporate Social Responsibility. She has been responsible for BIÓPTIMA, International Biomass and Energy Services Fair during his professional stage at the Institution of Fairs and Congresses of Jaén (Ferias Jaén S.A) and for the organization of the II Ibero-American Congress on Biorefineries. She is co-founder of Biliza and holds the position of director.

3.5.1 Description of the innovation process #1 Aceites Guadalentín

3.5.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial Idea

Virgilio started to modernise the family olive mill right from the start as company manager. These were times of change and modernisation in the olive oil sector and one of the first steps was, moving from the traditional press system (with circular hoods) to install an automatic three-stage centrifuge system. This allowed Aceites Guadalentín to obtain better and more constant quality oil. And so, he continued to implement small innovative changes in the mill until the end of the 80's.

In those times of continuous modernisation, olive oil mills sought to increase oil production. Hence, the mills continued to take steps, changing from the three-phase system to the new two-phase system that allowed even more oil to be extracted. This was also the case with Guadalentín oils in 1994.

THE ISSUE TO SOLVE: the management of the by-product

During Virgilio's early days as manager of Aceites Guadalentín, he had to deal with the management of by-products as part of the business activity. The general practice applied by most of the olive mills (either small, medium or large) was to send their by-products to the so called "orujeiras", also known as "extractors" which are companies

that collect the olive pomace from the mills and carry out a physical and chemical extraction process to obtain more oil, known as olive pomace oil.

This type of companies (extractors) has been in co-existing from long time, as a necessary part of the sector, to deal with and provide treatment to the olive pomace. These companies are processing in average a million of tonnes of olive pomace per year. Until the 1980s, these extractors acquired the pomace from the mills, which, using the traditional three-phase system, contained barely 60% moisture. Extractors were able to extract a significant fraction of the oil, making their business profitable, and therefore they used to purchase this feedstock to the olive mills.

As olive mills started installing the two-phase systems during the 90s, with higher oil extraction capacity, the pomace became impoverished as raw material for the olive oil pomace extractors. With lower oil content to be extracted, and with higher humidities (up to 70% in the case of two-phase processes) leading to more problems in the handling and drying processing and extracting olive pomace oil, the business was not balanced any more for olive pomace oil extractors.

This was the beginning of a problem for the sector, which still creates stresses in the sector nowadays. The extractors firstly had to adapt their industry to the new raw material, which is wetter, much more difficult to handle and dry, and has a lower oil content. The lower production, with higher operational costs and investments incurred by olive oil extractors, could only be compensated by lowering the purchase price of the olive pomace. This effect became more critical at the beginning of the 1990s, when, depending on the annual campaign, the pomace mills either stopped paying, or only offer to accept the olive pomace when delivered at plant gate and at zero cost. As a consequence, the olive oil mills began to have an additional cost, accompanied by uncertainty for the management of their by-product.

For Aceites Guadalentín, located in a remote rural area, managing the transport of its by-product to the olive pomace oil extractors was a problem year after year, since the nearest extractor was about 100 km away on local roads, which caused high time and transport costs. Moreover, depending on the season, conditions changed, and there was a tendency to not purchase the olive pomace by extractors, and the burden of the costs to incur by the olive mills.

Virgilio saw the management of the by-product (three-phase pomace, and later two-phase pomace, known as alpeorujo) as a key point in the business as early as the 1980s. It was in the 1990s that it became more critical, and Virgilio asked himself what he could do with the “orujo” pomace and the “alpechín” (aqueous phase of the 3 phase system), and later with the “alpeorujo” (when modernised to 2-phase process), in order to maintain his costs.

FIRST STEPS

The first steps were to use the “orujo” (three-phase olive pomace) during late 80s and early 90s and later the “alpeorujo” (two-stage olive pomace) after 1994 in the soil of their own olive groves. The idea was disruptive at that moment, as it was not recommended, and the farmers were reluctant, believing that it was a waste product that could contaminate or damage the productivity of the soil. Virgilio, saw the other side, which was an organic by-product with certain compounds that could provide fertility.

The new practice began in the early 1990s on its own, without any support or guidance from experts or scientists. It was in the mid-1990s, with the two-phase system in operation, and with the problem of alpeorujo management, that Aceites Guadalentín decided to invest in some ponds, to store it, even interannually, in order to be able to manage its own alpeorujo, given the problems and the costs involved in its delivery to the extractors. In such a way, they were able to not incur costs in years when the value was too low. And decide the best moment to sell or to apply to soil.

OIL SECTOR KNOWLEDGE EXPLOSION IN THE 1990s

During the 1980s, the information available on the sector, processes, innovation, and science was limited. Virgilio, always interested in knowing more, tells that during the 1990s there was an explosion of knowledge and dissemination in the sector.

Taking advantage of the increased availability of information, Virgilio keeps up to date by attending innovation forums, taking part in scientific and technical conferences at EXPOLIVA ([International fair of Olive Oil](#)), listening to programmes and reading the specialised press, etc. In addition, during 90s he established a close relationship with an expert from the “Instituto de la Grasa” (in Seville), a fundamental R&D centre for research into food lipids and oleaginous matter at the Spanish National Research Council - CSIC.

He found out more about the health benefits of olive products, among many other things. In addition, he followed with interest any possibility that could guide him to find an alternative in the management of olive pomace. While incorporation into the soil and sales provided less cost than transporting it to the extractors, he saw more potential in obtaining value from this by-product.

This allowed him to generate a second vision: of the valuable nutritional and health elements of the olive, only 2% remain in the oil. The rest (98%) remains in the by-product, especially in the aqueous fraction, the alpechín (which is a fraction with a very low pH, corrosive, and which in general no company wants or uses). It was curious that the highest value was given to the oil, because of its human nutritional function and its market, and that high-value substances remained mostly in the by-product, the management of which in the end implied a cost, and its management was oriented towards reduction and elimination.

At that time, it was important for Virgilio to find an environment in which to discuss and share ideas. His good relationship with one of the scientists at the “Instituto de la Grasa” (mentioned above) was very important, as it facilitated his learning. He also found other people in the area with the same concerns and open-mindedness to actively discuss the different alternatives. This environment gave him encouragement, to push himself and act, confirming his belief and vision, without thinking that his idea or vision was crazy.

NEXT STEPS: Composting?

A further step was taken in 1996 and 1997 when Virgilio wanted to find out about the possibilities of composting alpeorujo. He contracted a pilot project with his own funds to the University of Murcia. At that time he had already installed the two-phase system, and wanted to see the possibilities of composting the alpeorujo and obtaining a product that would be more suitable for the soil and at the same time more acceptable to the farmers.

The results were very good, and they observed that the compost had good quality. So, they continued the practice (until almost 2020), composting part of their own alpeorujo with other materials with a higher nitrogen content, using almost 50% of the alpeorujo on their own lands.

Of the remaining pomace, the established practice was to sun-dry them at the ponds and sell this dried fatty pomace as fuel to cogeneration plants or agro-industries. In some seasons also they derived part of this pomace to some olive pomace extractors.

SEEKING MORE VALUE

Encouraged by what he had learned throughout the 1990s about the different valuable fractions of alpeorujo, Virgilio decided to test solutions to obtain valuable fractions for cosmetics. At that time, his friends at the CSIC (Spanish National Research Council) shared with him that they already had phenol extraction processes.

So, with his own funds, Virgilio decided to set up a small experimental plant to test the extraction of valuable fractions from olive oil as first approach. Also with intend to explore potential chances to apply later on to the alpeorujo. This took place in the years 2003-2004 with his own money to create the small pilot facilities, and with research personnel in training provided by means of a collaboration with the Junta de Andalucía (regional government). Very promising results were obtained.

They started to explore ways to enter the market of supplying raw materials to cosmetics industry and in short time they had already validated products with several renowned major brands. However, they decided not to go for scaling up, or to explore the cosmetic ingredients from alpeorujo, as it was too different market for them, with channels and business models different from those of oil. They saw great complexity in establishing a secure supply contract, whilst a very significant investment was needed for the next steps.

They then began then to offer this opportunity to different potential investors or entrepreneurs, but they did not find any willing to start this path and scale it up. The experimental laboratory is currently still under use, but for a small production, it to produce small batches of cosmetic products that are part of the merchandising for Aceites Guadalentín.

CONSOLIDATING COMPOSTING, BUT WITHOUT VIABILITY

In 2005, it was then that the partners of Aceites Guadalentín (Virgilio and his brothers) decided to explore the chances to set up a new composting business as a new economic activity.

Before making the investment, they decided to check the market possibilities and the value the compost would have. They realised that, although the compost obtained was of very good quality, its commercialisation and economic return was very uncertain. On the one hand, the potential users of the compost, farmers in the area, were not interested in paying sufficient for it. It was not a standard synthetic "fertiliser" product with immediate action, like chemical fertilisers, but a slower-acting soil improver, which did not enter the farmer's perception of "value".

Given the investments to be made, the lack of motivated customers, and the low price at which they could sell it, they saw that it was not going to be an economically sustainable activity and decided in 2005 not to continue with the enormous investment necessary to establish the composting plant. Therefore Virgilio, as company manager, started to look for the best way to manage the olive pomace.

FIRST STEP ON THE ROAD TO become a BIOINDUSTRY.

Virgilio continued for some years to assess the possibilities and to learn about possible solutions to solve the recurrent problem of olive pomace management campaign after campaign.

He was aware of the options to further extract more oil from the olive pomace, similarly to what "extractors" were doing. So, the decision was to install such a facility, that would provide some revenues (by obtaining a portion of the remaining oil in the pomace), but also to generate by-products more easy to be handled. Virgilio decided to set up his own local olive extractor facility, doing only physical operations, not chemical operations, that allow further extraction, and which is usually the method applied by olive pomace extractors.

In 2012, Aceites Guadalentín built an alperujo reprocess plant, with ponds and a building for the process's physical repass (not including chemical extraction of olive pomace oil). It was initially designed for the treatment of its own olive pomace, but it also considered the possibility of collecting olive pomace from other olive mills in the area once the plant worked properly.

After the start of the installation, as foreseen, the olive oil mills in the area (which had the same problems of distance to extractors, costs, and instability from year to year) joined and started procuring the olive pomace to Aceites Guadalentín, thus reducing their costs with respect to delivery to the extractors. Thus, they gradually invested in increasing the capacity of the ponds and the processing capacity.

The process they followed in Guadalentín was similar to that of other extractors with reprocess facilities, by the difference that here they carried out the drying in the sun, whereas the usual practice was the use of forced drying into rotating trommels. They stated that, at least at that time, nobody else was doing it, they were pioneers in this sun-drying practice they had learned and applied during the last 2 decades.

A NEW PROBLEM TO BE SOLVED: ENERGY

The newly built olive pomace oil extraction plant required electricity for its operation. However, as the reprocessing plant was located far from the grid, it had to generate its own electricity with a diesel generator. This generated significant energy bills, and Aceites Guadalentín began to consider how to reduce their costs. On the one hand, in 2016 they started the process to request the power grid to be extended to get connected to grid, even though the costs were high.

On the other hand, they knew what the general practice was done in other olive pomace oil extractors: the plants installed gas-powered electricity cogeneration systems that fed into the grid and used the derived heat to dry the pomace in a trommel. Here the solution would be similar, but with diesel-powered engines. They commissioned the project, and already in 2016 they had the project ready for investment.

But Virgilio waited as the idea of the dryer with diesel cogeneration, similar to that of other extractors, did not really convince them. They were aware of the reality in other areas, where these installations generated fumes, strong odours and rejection by the local population. And they saw that this could be a problem for Aceites Guadalentín. In addition, given the strong impact on other areas, they feared that the project would be stalled due to delays in obtaining environmental licenses.

Inspiration

REORIENTING, LOOKING FOR THE CIRCULAR SOLUTION

During 2016-2017, Virgilio's conviction led him to keep looking for a way to get value from the by-product, and at the same time, to solve the electricity supply problem. However, he had no idea how to tackle it.

It was then that he began to hear about the proposal and vision of BIOLIZA, which, in some publications and in some forums, talked about gasification as a solution for alpeorujo management, allowing electricity to be generated.

In March 2017, Virgilio attended the World Olive Oil Exhibition (WOOE, in Madrid), knowing that José Antonio La Cal was taking part in the technical conferences, with a presentation entitled: "Energy valuation of olive by-products as elements in the fight against climate change and the improvement of the sector's competitiveness" ([link to programme](#)).

He decided to call him the following week. José Antonio la Cal and Isabel Cano-Caballero (BIOLIZA director) tolds him that they were working on another project at that moment, but began to provide Virgilio with information. Short time later this industrial project of BIOLIZA (actually the second) failed right before undesigning the contract). Then BIOLIZA and Virgilio contacted again, to explore the possibilities for Guadalentín.

3.5.1.2 Implementation phase

Planning

It is during 2018 that José Antonio La Cal from BIOLIZA, contacts back Virgilio to offer him his consultancy to install an alpeorujo gasification system that will allow him to obtain electricity and heat. A project very similar to the two pilots with which BIOLIZA had reached very advanced stages.

At that time BIOLIZA also had a compromise for subsidy from the Junta de Andalucía (regional government) for this purpose (which was not going to be used for the previous project).

Virgilio noted the advanced state of knowledge and implementation ability, thanks to the path that BIOLIZA had already taken with previous clients. Virgilio's questions were answered and everything seemed very coherent. BIOLIZA state of knowledge, technical solvency, previous path learned, was key to gaining Guadalentín's trust, with the fact that the regional government agreed to subsidise part of the investment. The conversations with technicians helped to build confidence in the viability of the project.

This helped establish a collaborative tandem from the start. They started to make decisions hand in hand jointly. Selecting ANKUR technologists, who was more distant but European providers offered much more expensive solutions, and gave no sufficient guarantees for the operation with this, up to the moment, unexplored fuel.

They chose a safer solution, although not without risk. Virgilio has full confidence in José Antonio's and Isabel Cano-Caballero knowledge. He was convinced by the clear vision they had. And that even as consultants, BIOLIZA was even decided to act as EPC and take responsibility for the plant. The most valuable issue for Virgilio was the confidence and compromise from BIOLIZA.

Development

The contract between Guadalentín and BIOLIZA was signed at the end of 2018, in which BIOLIZA acts as EPC. This is because it was the only way to access the subsidy. Virgilio understands the role of BIOLIZA beyond consultant. Virgilio accepts to collaborate in a flexible way in this innovative project.

The first thing that was done was to send biomass samples for characterisation, testing and validation, as it was a very specific and very local biomass not known to ANKUR. Then, based on the energy demands of the client (Aceites Guadalentín, S.L.), the project was sized and the total investment was quantified.

During 2018-2019 they had a very extensive contact with ANKUR. They exchanged emails, had multiple video conferences.

Realisation

There were many critical moments during this process. One of them was the arrival of the gasifier in 20 containers from India. Firstly, because half of the containers were stopped due to COVID restrictions at the beginning of 2020. Secondly, because the assembly was not carried out by ANKUR. The whole immense puzzle had to be assembled by an engineering company, which had already located BIOLIZA in advance thanks to its previous work.

Another problem that arose was environmental permitting. The administration that managed the industrial activity permits suggested it required a licence for agricultural or agro-industrial activity. The department of agricultural and agro-industrial permits understood that it was a competent installation for industry.

Virgilio decided to go ahead. Even without having secured the permits, which finally they got in the end of 2021. This barrier had already caused other initiatives to fail. But Virgilio persisted. The pioneer is risking by adopting a new technology. And then the permitting administration doesn't make it easy. But Virgilio was a seasoned manager with much experience. After 30 years at the head of the company, he had been forced on more than one occasion to go ahead, and not to stop because of these issues. His ability to take risks was key. This uncertainty of permits made others to fail.

3.5.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

Aceites Guadalentín's cogeneration gasification plant is the first of its kind in the world. It is located in Pozo Alcón, a remote rural town in the province of Jaén, the Spanish province with the largest olive grove surface area, and where there is a need to advance in a more sustainable, circular management and to get the best value from olive oil by-products.

During the implementation process, Aceites Guadalentín and BIOLIZA saw how the administration and the industrial sector itself did not trust the real viability of the alternative they intended to implement. However, once construction was underway, they were eager to know the outcome. Once built and in operation:

- (1) Politicians themselves came to see it and were so surprised (not believe their eyes), even if they had been told about it.
- (2) Virgilio indicates that they got as feedback that Guadalentín innovation is a model to be replicated.
- (3) The administration's technicians understand the scheme and are convinced.

- (4) Public and private actors note that it does not generate the noxious and abundant emissions that are a problem in other areas, due to the CHP drying plants and the olive pomace extractors.
- (5) Even some companies that visit Guadalentín want Virgilio himself to get involved in their projects because even after seeing in operation, the challenge of being the second, the third brings doubts (feel afraid, unsecure).

Due to its success and the effect it can drive in the sector, Aceites Guadalentín has received two awards from the Diputación de Jaén (Local government of the Jaen Province), one of them for the "Global Business Project".

Embedding

Guadalentín's objective is not to enter the business of replicating his case in other mills. Virgilio continues to maintain the vision he forged in the 1990s: olive mills generate 75 to 80% of by-products, which contain the vast majority of high-value compounds from the olive.

The gasification of the fatty olive pomace is only a first stage, which allows Aceites Guadalentín to maintain a self-sufficient energy supply system that enables it to reduce energy costs and establish a drying system. The gasifier is used to recover up to 20% of the olive pomace production but the remaining 80%, once it has undergone reprocessing operations, is sold as fuel for industrial heating, cement factories, dryers, greenhouses, etc.

In addition, it has installed an innovative system for separating the olive stones, which allows Aceites Guadalentín to obtain clean, dry stones, to be sold as solid, certified quality biofuel. Also, the biochar obtained from gasification as a by-product has proven to be of high quality. The next step is to find a niche market for it.

The pomace that is not used in the gasifier and the alpechín (aqueous fraction) remain an issue to be solved. At the moment the treatment is solar drying and selling to other energy facilities. But this fraction will be the subject of the next steps: generating biogas, and/or extracting the fertilising mineral compounds. Aceites Guadalentín has already applied for an industrial innovation project in these lines.

Another way is to expand biochar production. First they need to consolidate the sales, channels and value of biochar from gasification. After that, they will see if it is worth making a specific investment, depending on the value, which Virgilio believes will be high, thanks to the high lignin content of the bone.

Another pending route is to consolidate the pilot production of bioproducts for the cosmetics market in the future, in order to provide a greater outlet and diversify the products. In principle, not on the basis of Aceites Guadalentín own investment, but through collaboration with another company that wishes to undertake the investment and manage the marketing.

3.5.2 Timeline #1 Aceites Guadalentín

Figure 5: Timeline – Aceites Guadalentín

3.5.3 Main characteristics #1 Aceites Guadalentin

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Aceites Guadalentin innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Early modernisation and implementation of small innovative changes - The sector face lower oil content (business is not well balanced) face increased costs - Diverse steps toward the by-product management (uses soil, sales to agro-industries, experimental plant...) - Looking for alternatives and learning from press, forum and relationship with an R&D centre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Uncertainty in managing by-products (cost, time, logistic...) - To find other people with to actively discuss - Engage own funds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert at “Instituto de la Grasa” (R&D centre) and Spanish National Research Council - Regional government (Junta de Andalucía)
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Learn about Bioliza proposition and first contact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Connected with media, forums, press, event (e.g. World Olive Oil Exhibition) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bioliza
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proposition to install gasification system - Subsidy from the regional government - Select technologist - Bioliza take an EPC role 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building trust is essential - EU providers/technologist are much more expensive - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bioliza - ANKUR (Indian technologist)
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Signing of the contract between BIOLIZA. - Accessing the subsidy. - Sending biomass samples for characterisation, testing, and validation. - Sizing a quantifying based on the energy demands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous exchange with ANKUR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - BIOLIZA - ANKUR
	Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Arrival and installation of the gasifier 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Gasifier came in 20 containers from India. - Need and uncertainty to have environmental permits - Risk to adopt a new technology (as pioneer) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engineering company - The department of agricultural and agro-industrial permits
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First gasification plant of its kind in the world - Gaining traction and interest to visit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - N/A 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - political representatives, administration's technicians

		- Received two awards		- Industrial, companies and private actors - Local government of the Jaen Province
	Embedding	- maintain a self-sufficient energy supply system - Installation of improved processing technique and looking for a niche market - Open for new relevant investment and innovative opportunities	- Continue the vision forged without to try to necessary replicate - consolidate the sales, channels. Value and pilot production (e.g. biochar from gasification, bioproducts for the cosmetics...)	N/A

Table 5: Overview of characteristics - Aceites Guadalentin

3.5.4 Description of the innovation process #2 Bioliza

3.5.4.1 Initiation phase

Initial Idea

Born and living in Jaén, the province of Spain with the largest surface area of olive groves, José Antonio La Cal has been for long time aware of the needs of the olive sector, specifically about the management of the main by-product, the olive pomace (, which is the result of extracting mechanically oil in the olive mills pomace), which average annual production in Spain is about 1 million tons. The management of such amount of olive pomace, due to its moisture content has been always an issue, and already from his position at the energy agency of Jaén AGENER (2004-2012) he perceived that there were alternatives for its management. He was witness to the rapid expansion of natural gas cogeneration plants as solution in Andalusia. Thanks to a very generous feed-in tariff, they were profitable to operate by using natural gas in engines to generate electricity and to obtain derived heat as a source of heat for drying the olive cake.

The idea of gasification as an enabling technology for circularity goes back 10 years (2013), before BIOLIZA was founded. The primary thought was: gas to evaporate water? And the spark came: If we have a lot of biomass, and we need a lot of gas... how do we connect opportunity with need? And he started to research and learn more about biomass gasification, which was a technology that was hardly known in Spain.

The main idea had to do with the enormous potential of biomass from the olive grove and its related industries and the need to find solutions for its valorisation, including gasification. He had the following vision:

- (1) Business idea: The idea was therefore to respond to an important need, which was to use partially part of the production of the olive pomace, process residue from the oil industry, to dry the olive pomace coming from the olive mills instead of using fossil fuels (natural gas) that it is expensive and polluting.
- (2) Market: he saw that there was no competition. It was an innovative and almost transgressive idea, because gasification was still a very unknown technology in Spain, even preceded by bad practices, so the challenge was even greater, as there was more resistance to overcome.
- (3) Benefits: gasification technology makes possible to develop models under the paradigm of the circular economy, generate savings, solve the management of a by-product that generates a high transport cost and it was normally dry in olive extraction facilities by means of fossil fuels. By this new method, new products were obtained and energy costs were reduced besides environmental intangibles.

Inspiration

In previous years he had started his doctoral studies, up to the degree of Master Science. In 2012, after finishing his work at AGENER, he thought of investing his personal time in developing his PhD on gasification. In 2013 he defended the PhD thesis, with very practical orientation, and as a means to gain more knowledge (PhD thesis title "Feasibility of the integration of a biomass gasification plant").

After finishing his PhD, with a clearer technical and feasibility vision, he began "his journey", his personal commitment to provide solutions for the management of olive oil industry by-products by means of gasification. In his path he was supported always by Isabel Cano-Caballero, wife, and from 2014, director of Bioliza.

As technology expert, José Antonio first step was to began to contact companies in Spain. He kept looking for a technologist with whom he could form an alliance to generate a first pilot project. But he realised that the way was always closed by most of the technology providers offering gasification, whose main lines of business were others, and gasification was a minor line of business or a line without projection, in comparison to their main business lines (waste, engineering, petrochemicals). Therefore, José Antonio La Cal and Isabel Cano-Caballero could not get technologists being compromised allies with solid interest to get involved in a pilot project in a company in the olive oil sector. No technologist showed interest to explore the opportunity, which meant sharing risks but opening up to future benefits.

It was in 2015 when it began BIOLIZA relationship with ANKUR, a technologist from India, whose main line of business is gasification. He identified this company as a reliable supplier, with extensive experience in this field, mainly in Asia and in certain African and South American countries. BIOLIZA began then to create a fluid relationship, to receive information, answers, and interests. Then José Antonio and Isabel find the first cornerstone is solved, there is already a compromised technologist. The next step is to get the first customer, and industry from the olive oil sector.

Start-up and first steps

In the meantime, José Antonio continued to work in parallel to his usual work, giving courses and as an associate lecturer at the University of Jaén. It was there that a turning point occurred.

Convinced that the idea of gasifying olive by-products is a viable route, José Antonio and Isabel published papers and submitted ideas to competitions, and obtained 2 prizes by the University of Jaén between 2012-2013, and published a book. In 2013 the prize awarded consisted in an endowment of 3000 Euros to create a Limited Company (SL), and access to free office space for 6 months as a spin-off of the University of Jaén. BIOLIZA Estrategias en Biomasa SL is born, with headquarters in the GEOLIT Science and Technology Park in Mengíbar (Jaén).

Receiving the award was the key. Those 3000 euros, and the short 6 months for a free office. José Antonio declares himself as a person with vision and passion for the olive grove, energy and technology. But not as an entrepreneur, as his professional life was until then linked to public administration and teaching. However, he decided to create BIOLIZA, a company through which he could carry out consultancy work, invoicing for this professional activity. It was decided to set up the company and to focus on gasification as a technology. And to count on with Isabel Cano as support in commercial and managerial aspects of the company.

RECURSOS ESTRATÉGICOS DE BIOMASA, S.L., which is the legal name of BIOLIZA, is a company incorporated in May 2014 and focused on the development of biomass/bioenergy projects in 3 areas:

- (1) Consulting/engineering
- (2) Training
- (3) Development and implementation of biomass gasification projects

It is a Spin Off of the University of Jaén, due to the fact that one of the partners is José Antonio La Cal, Associate Lecturer at the University.

Starting to operate without income. First decisions

The beginnings were hard, as once the 6 months of grace period for the payment of office (telephone, electricity...) was over, the company moved to new premises in March 2015, in the incubator of Technology-Based Companies of the University of Jaén. BIOLIZA begins to have to face more payments. At the same time, the work starts to demand more hours. In order to invoice it is also necessary to invest more time in establishing incomes and managing the company.

In response to this need, another key decision is taken that keeps BIOLIZA alive. The administrator of BIOLIZA, José Anto'io's wife, who until then had been working in her spare time, left her job to dedicate herself plenty to BIOLIZA as director, in order to have more options to get contracts for courses, small consultancies and new clients. It thus becomes a fully family-run business. At the same time, they redouble their efforts to find a successful industrial pilot that positions them as a reference facilitator for the sector in which they see a great opportunity.

First customers, first jobs, looking for the first pilot

The strategy to follow was to maintain BIOLIZA with a remunerated activity with small consultancies, and carrying out advisory tasks, with a cost in time, but not in high expenses. This would allow BIOLIZA to maintain the promotion and launching activity for the pilot with low costs. In the meantime, they were looking for a client with whom implementing a first pilot with the help of the technologist ANKUR.

In 2016 BIOLIZA began a search for customers, seeking one to take the first step to establish a first pilot case to serve as a reference. José Antonio and Isabel contacted olive oil mills, industries, and attended to events. They explained the benefits of gasification and their great potential. After a while, BIOLIZA started receiving calls with the first requests for collaboration.

However, as BIOLIZA progressed with each client, they realised that something always was going wrong. At first the clients showed interest, but as the project preparation progressed, the clients lost interest and drop out. They just couldn't get them engaged till the moment of investment. So on and so forth. They realised some of them lost interest quickly when they saw that there was no previous reference, that it was not an established product. Or that they were going to be the first. But between 2016 and 2018 BIOLIZA managed to make progress with 2 clients reaching very mature stages: with the feasibility study done and the official subsidy to cover part of the investment granted. Unfortunately, when the time came to formalise contracts, the clients did not take the step of contracting the work to BIOLIZA and ANKUR.

They realised it was an issue of trust, doubts and fear of the risk, that were stronger for the companies than the opportunity.

Surviving 4 years without hitting the industrial pilot (2015-2018)

In the meantime, BIOLIZA got incomes only for courses and consultancy contracts (even not always covering the costs of travel, materials, etc. or the time spent). So, doubts arose about continuing and finishing the company on several occasions.

BIOLIZA knows Aceites Guadalentín. How did they start collaborating?

2017, José Antonio continues to attend events, give talks and continue his teaching activity. On one of these occasions, at a presentation in Madrid on 29 March, as part of the "WOOE - World Olive Oil Exhibition" (see programme), he gave a presentation on his vision of gasification as a key solution for olive mills and olive oil industry sector. The WOOE event is an unrivalled forum, but, nevertheless, only 4 people attended his presentation. He came back disappointed with the result but one of the 4 attendees, Virgilio Gámez, calls the following week. He was the owner of Aceites Guadalentín, a small oil mill in a remote and isolated village. At that moment, José Antonio gives him information, but does not exploit the contact. And BIOLIZA continues to focus on one of his previous clients, with whom he approaches at the moment of formalising the contract.

During 2017-2018, BIOLIZA dedicates itself to the development of a first pilot. It goes a long way with two pioneers. But at the moment of investment, the companies decided to give up.

BIOLIZA does not give up. In 2018, it resumes contact with Guadalentín. The success story begins to take shape. Once again, it is BIOLIZA's vision and perseverance that allows it to move forward. Following their vision despite every setback: they see the huge opportunity, clear market, little competition, many benefits that would make that after a first plant the experience would be extended.

3.5.4.2 Implementation phase

Planning

The decision making: a key moment when previous pilots had given up. A lesson in trust and risk sharing

Once the feasibility study is accepted, they move on to the implementation phase. BIOLIZA takes the decision to move from consultant, to a more risky position the role of EPC (Engineering, Procurement and Construction) with responsibility to build the plant. The reason is that in order to receive the subsidy from the Andalusian Energy Agency, it was necessary for the final recipient (Aceites Guadalentín) to carry out the work (and obtain the subsidy) through a "collaborating entity" in charge of executing the works as EPC (this is a means of the Andalusian government to provide more transparency and ensure good use of the subsidy money). BIOLIZA invoices the 3 M€ for the investment and starts work as EPC.

Clients contracting and EPC may ask for some clauses in the contract to be on the safe side and reduce its own risks. For example, by being very strict in times and compensations under the event of delays, or by asking the EPC a guarantee of 80% of investment in advance. This type of manoeuvre to reduce risk on the part of the end client was not requested by Aceites Guadalentín, who placed its trust and worked with BIOLIZA in tandem (hand in hand). He realised the trust was the key, and both in tandem were solving problems together. Bioliza further concludes that on this path of risk, of putting in your own time and capital, over years, the luck factor is also necessary.

Development

The contract between Guadalentín and BIOLIZA was signed at the end of 2018, with BIOLIZA acting as EPC. The first thing that was done was to send biomass samples for characterisation, testing and validation, as it was a very specific and very local biomass not known to ANKUR. Then, based on the energy demands of the client (Aceites Guadalentín, S.L.), the project was sized, and the total investment was quantified.

During 2018-2019 they have a very extensive contact with ANKUR. They exchange emails and have video conferences.

Realisation

ANKUR is visited by Virgilio and José Antonio in 2019. After the visit, the ANKUR contract was signed, and ANKUR carried out the gasifier engineering in 2019.

Finally, all the necessary steps were taken to get it up and running, including obtaining the financial incentive that had already been compromised previously. BIOLIZA's role as coordinator, as it has had to look for companies of all kinds for the construction and start-up, always with the support of the technologist ANKUR and with the total complicity of Aceites Guadalentín. Other engineering firms have also been involved in the technical side (projects, legalisations, construction, environmental procedures, etc.). The choices, budgets and deadlines were in line with expectations, hence the successful outcome of this first plant of its kind.

For the development of the project, a loan has been requested from a credit institution and has been supported by the main socio-economic agents in the area, one of the main barriers being the time required for the processing of permits and authorisations, despite having public support. This is one of the main barriers to the development of this type of project.

The installation phase took place in 2020, during the period of the COVID pandemic, when the equipment was on order, but with delays due to difficulties in transporting and moving personnel.

Some key actors and items involved were:

- (1) The Andalusian Energy Agency (AAE) is key because it provides the economic incentive. Moreover, because of the validation provided by the AAE: it provides the client (Aceites Guadalentín) confidence that what is being financed is seriously and that it is not a risky idea (otherwise it would not be subsidised).
- (2) ANKUR facilitator. It was very serious, creditworthy and very efficient company. Also, open to changes and improvements in the project (for example, using SIEMENS motors instead of others that raised more doubts for the promoter).
- (3) Guadalentín's confidence, which, in addition to the reluctance to use the technology and to be the first, has also been overcome thanks to the support of the Andalusian Energy Agency, which, with the incentive, has partly compensated for this possible uncertainty.
- (4) Agroóleum, which was a local engineering company well known by Aceites Guadalentín, was very cooperative. Civil works, etc. Open to every change, problem, to solve it with the property and with the work needs of BIOLIZA who worked as EPC.

Another key item was obtaining the environmental permits. Here Virgilio's temperance and experience was key. He did not stop the investment waiting to have the permits to start operation in hand and went ahead even though he had no certainty that the administration would process it favorably (it was a novel plant, first of its type). Permits finally arrived on time in November 2021. The project was completed in February 2022.

3.5.4.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

For dissemination purposes, BIOLIZA (and Aceites Guadalentín) have participated in several forums, events, conferences, fairs, etc., both nationally and internationally, showing the project. A video of the project has also been made through a European project (AgroBioHeat) that sought to disseminate lighthouse projects ([see video](#)) and numerous visits have been organised to companies, universities and research centres which had high interest in visiting the plant. Articles have also been written in specialised magazines, and publicity has been given on social networks, such as LinkedIn, mainly. The case has also been documented as an Innovative Practice in the [European BRANCHES project](#) (info [in Spanish](#) and [English](#)), disseminated to other countries through thematic networks, and made available on the EIP-AGRI portal.

The promotional activities of BIOLIZA and Aceites Guadalentín have played a key role in all of this. AVEBIOM has been a key collaborating agent, facilitating the visualisation of the case at the 2021 and 2022 International Bioenergy Congress (in Spanish language, organised by AVEBIOM), in several webinars, and in AVEBIOM's dissemination media (magazine, newsletters). AVEBIOM is also one of the partners of AgroBioHeat and BRANCHES projects.

Embedding

No replication has been implemented. It is at that stage, despite being an innovative project, whose viability has been demonstrated with this first pilot project, the next stage of expansion is being more difficult than expected due to the lack of confidence that potential customers still have in the solution. It would be desirable other gasification references to exist in order to generate sufficient confidence in the sector so that this solution would be envisioned as creditworthy. Notwithstanding the response from those who visit the plant is usually positive, although it is another matter whether it fits in with technical and strategic approaches.

The circular economy and the decarbonisation objectives of companies makes it foreseeable that in a few years there will be more projects like this one, although perhaps evolving more slowly than expected, especially in these early stages of innovation and implementation.

BIOLIZA remains focused on being a consultancy specialised in biomass, and in accompanying and guiding the implementation of gasification systems in industry. They continue to be guided and convinced by the huge opportunity, especially now that companies see the value of not depending on gas.

Based on the consultancy for new industrial projects the customers are the industries that consume gas or generate biomass. Not only olive oil and olive pomace oil extractors facilities , but other customers are also more likely to be breweries, malt production companies, ceramic kilns, drying industries of agricultural products, etc.

Future prospects.

- (1) Continue to expand to other sectors. The pieces are settling down. They are beginning to bear fruit.
- (2) Next projects, now that the solvency of the solution has been demonstrated, take fewer risks for BIOLIZA: Do not act as EPC again and have it done by a specialised company, with good financial back-up and able to work with other customer profiles (not necessarily highly motivated, flexible and collaborating as Aceites Guadalentín was).
- (3) BIOLIZA is dedicated to the consultancy of the technological solution.
- (4) Patented/protected: the solution is unique and innovative but cannot be patented or protected, although formulas for doing so have been analysed.
- (5) Establish a work team, with profiles combining knowledge, enthusiasm and patience

3.5.5 Timeline #2 Bioliza

Figure 6: Timeline – Bioliza

3.5.6 Main characteristics #2 Bioliza

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Bioliza innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being aware of regional needs and opportunities - Research and development of business idea 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing a vision valorize over years. - Limited knowledge of biomass gasification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AGENER (energy agency)
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing a PhD thesis and looking for first pilot project - Receiving an award and establishing a consultancy company - Searching for potential clients to establish the first pilot plant - Presenting on gasification at events and establishing contacts - First contact with Aceites Guadalentín 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initiating contacts with companies focus on gasification - Publishing papers, a book, and submitting to competitions - Facing company payments while administering - Finding a committed and confident technology partner for a pilot project. - Skepticism due to past practices of potential customers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ANKUR (technologist) - Incubator (Technology-Based Companies of the University of Jaén) - Isabel Cano-Caballero (José Antonio's wife) become 100% time dedicated to BIOLIZA - Aceites Guadalentín
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conducting a feasibility study - Bioliza take an EPC (Engineering, Procurement, and Construction) role and ensuring a support subsidy - Start investment to initiate the project. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The turn from a consultant to an EPC role increased responsibility and risks. - Subsidy terms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Andalusian Energy Agency - Aceites Guadalentín
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formalizing collaboration with ANKUR - Local biomass for assessment and quantifying 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consistent communication - Adapt to the specific energy demand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aceites Guadalentín - ANKUR
	Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financing of the project - Collaborative engineering and coordinative efforts, involving multiple technical aspects - Execution of the installation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Obtaining necessary permits and authorizations - Logistic delays in equipment orders due to the pandemic. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Andalusian Energy Agency - Agroóleum (engineering company)
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Participation in various forums, events, conferences, and publicity through specialized press and social networks - Involvement in European projects (video, cross-visits) - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AVEBIOM has been a key collaborating agent, facilitating the visualisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aceites Guadalentín - AVEBIOM (Biomass association) - EIP-AGRI portal
	Embedding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consultation services for new industrial projects and sectors - Promoting creditworthiness in the industry. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Replication is still difficult due to remaining potential customers' skepticism. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Industries that consume gas or generate biomass

		- Efforts to establish a committed work team.		
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Table 6: Overview of characteristics – Bioliza

3.6 Forest debris management and fire prevention by Sciven – Portugal

Company profile information

The company was founded in 2012 and, initially, it had the purpose of researching and developing the base technology. This was the main activity during the first 7/8 years. Sciven’s solutions are based on two main technologies: cogeneration (production of electrical energy from a heat source) in small scale and low temperature (which is, by itself, innovative and it cannot be found anywhere else in the European market), and thermal centrals fuelled by biomass, of 150-500 kW per boiler, having the option of grouping multiple boilers, as well.

Sciven’s products and services are engineering solutions to supply the energy needs (thermal and electric) of its clients, preferably by assembling both cogeneration systems and biomass-fuelled thermal centrals, but also by integrating other kinds of equipments (eg. heat pumps, boilers using different fuels) or simply by optimizing energy efficiency. The company’s turnover was 800 000 euros and it has currently 7 employees working in full-time, 5 employees working in part-time on a permanent basis, and 3 other collaborators that cannot be considered as permanent employees.

Contact profile information

Eduardo Costa studied Mechanical Engineering at the Faculty of Science and Technology of the University of Coimbra (UC), having graduated in 2008 with a master’s degree. Before founding Sciven, his experience was based on the research work he carried out during and little after his academic education.

The research work carried out after his graduation still took place in UC, and in discussions with some of his colleagues still finishing their master’s degree and their respective guiding teachers, the concept of energy production through micro cogeneration originated. In 2012, the idea got interesting enough to justify the start of a company with the goal of developing the technology needed.

At first, the company was more of an instrument to support the development of the base technology and its demonstration at a micro scale (5 kWe). Eduardo’s functions, back then, were those of a junior engineer supported by the coordination of senior founders. Nowadays, his functions are the general coordination, prospection of new businesses, either new clients or new technological opportunities, and the establishment of external relations.

3.6.1 Description of the innovation process

3.6.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial idea

The initial idea emerged from the observation that any production of thermal energy, for any purpose, was an opportunity for producing electrical energy too. It came up to Eduardo and his colleagues in discussions about the research work each of them was carrying out in their master’s degree or little after graduation. This idea then grew around the practical challenge of understanding the viability of supplying the thermal energy needs of the Mechanical Engineering Department through micro cogeneration.

The advantage of this innovation and general idea since the beginning is the reduction of the expenditure with energy consumption.

Inspiration

Eduardo and his colleagues entered a program called *Arrisca Coimbra*, which was a contest for entrepreneurship ideas, and they won the first-place prize for best business plan. They were able to capitalise on this and started

meeting with investors. However, this led them to realize that they needed a true business plan despite just having won a prize for that.

In 2011, they participated in an intensive training program organized by COTEC Portugal, which selects 10 projects from all over the country to have training during 6 months about business themes, such as marketing, management, or finances, with American trainers from great universities that encourage the participants to develop a business plan. That program turned out to be very important for understanding the technology development in a structured way, enabling its demonstration, and figuring out what products could be extracted from it, and ultimately, they were able to develop the business plan that they needed.

Besides that, the main item on which Eduardo and his colleagues were able to capitalise was the ecosystem of the UC, mainly the experience of the teachers who became the senior founders of Sciven, Prof. José Baranda (who is the main collaborator for Biorural from the UC), Prof. Ricardo Mendes and Prof. Jorge André. These were the key actors involved in the development of the idea since the beginning.

3.6.1.2 Implementation phase

Planning

The planning activities started with the application for the system of support and incentive for R&D projects of the regional economic and social cohesion policy program (QREN), at the same time that the company was founded (2012), which predicated the existence of a technological plan for 3 years, in order to demonstrate the technology on a defined scale, and a financial plan for 3 years also.

The key actors in this phase were the same as before (the senior founders), who spent much of their own time in favour of the new-born company's success. The business incubator of Instituto Pedro Nunes (IPN), where the company has been based since its inception, allowed Sciven to capitalise on the community of existent companies, drawing good practices and professional mechanisms from them.

Development

The development activities started at December of 2012 by aiming to develop the first micro cogeneration prototype, intended for domestic use. That was achieved in 2015, with a cogeneration unit capable of producing between 1 and 5 kWe. This period was the first stage in the development of the innovation. However, the domestic sector is too big and dominated by two or three main players, and Sciven was just too "small" for that challenge. Even though they had conversations with a big international brand of boilers in order to integrate their cogeneration units to their catalogue, they soon realized that was not the best strategy.

In the final months of 2015, Sciven faced a crossroads: finding the best way of ending the company or searching for more investment and delivering another solution, because the budget for those past three years had been spent and there was not a final product that could create value in the market, as the investors wanted. In that moment began a second stage, when they decided to scale-up the technology (to 50 kWe) for target clients with greater energy needs that could more likely benefit from it. They also decided to couple the cogeneration technology to the use of biomass as fuel for the heat source because, as the development of the technology advanced, it was clear that if the cogeneration system operated using heat produced from a renewable and cheaper source than the traditional ones, the economic efficiency of the system would greatly benefit.

This led to the establishment of a partnership with a biomass-fuelled boilers manufacturer. However, the clients that could benefit from the implementation of a biomass-fuelled system had, many times, requirements such as reliability, ease of use and even architectonic integration that the available boilers at the time could not fulfil. For the next 2-3 years, they tried to develop the new solution, but were forced to spend 60-70% of the time fixing problems with the biomass-fuelled boilers, as their manufacturer was less evolved than expected, engineering-wise. Therefore, at the end of this period, they still had not advanced as much as they needed, and they still had

not a finished product to be competitive in the market. At this point, the investors were “jumping off”, so the company had necessarily to rebuild its team of employees and change their strategy once again.

This time, they would not continue with the partnership with the boilers manufacturer, and they would launch their own line of biomass-fuelled boilers, their respective accessories, and integrated technical rooms. It was at this stage that the partnership between Sciven and Biomass Centre for Energy (CBE) started. As a result of Sciven’s compromise to provide a customer with a solution dependent on biomass supply, CBE elaborated the study for its assurance. Then, due to the familiarity between CBE and Directorate-General of Energy and Geology (DGEG), Sciven’s participation in many projects was facilitated by the latter.

A link with an incubator from Penela was also established at this stage and proved to be fruitful, leading to the contact with many of the municipalities that are a good part of Sciven’s clients today. This growing network of contacts was the main item on which Sciven was able to capitalise during the development of the innovation.

Realisation

The innovation was delivered to the first client in the end of 2019. The most significant step that led Sciven to this milestone was originated by the urgency of generating an income because the technological development could not keep going without having a revenue of some kind. That was the moment when Sciven took the biomass-fuelled boilers responsibility for itself and started to provide that solution to its first clients.

The advantage of this innovation and general idea is the reduction of the expenditure of energy consumption while decarbonizing it, at the same time. The main difference is that the initial idea only involved the production and selling of the machinery, whilst nowadays the goal is to provide the whole energetic service. That involves the logistic of the fuel supply, the operation and maintenance of the equipments, and the creation of remote management platforms in order to allow a preventive maintenance.

The product is still not patented nor licensed, although that is expected to happen with the evolution of the company’s maturity, since it requires an autonomous financial effort.

3.6.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

The product was launched in the end of 2019. The dissemination of the solution happened in different stages. First, it happened through the network already cultivated by the company, and then through various opportunities such as participation in projects, conferences, and fairs. Nowadays, the company also relies on external collaborators for the assurance of business opportunities.

The link that Sciven still has with UC, and later with CBE, allows the company to disseminate in its areas of influence, in which opportunities emerge such as the participation in projects. Furthermore, the company’s base in IPN incubator allows Sciven to have permanent contact with a technology-based ecosystem of companies, which also contributes to the dissemination of its solutions.

The main challenge in this phase is the persuasion of the most sceptical consumers, which would sometimes have a great benefit from Sciven’s solutions, but due to disbelief and/or lethargy, cannot be convinced to take action.

Embedding

Eduardo does not consider that Sciven’s innovation has become a common practice yet, in part because it is not a product for the masses. Furthermore, when it comes to implement a solution involving the integration of a sustainable biomass supply chain, there are still some barriers that lead to uncertainty about the project. On the other hand, when fully implemented, the solutions cause so much impact that other end-users become enticed to adopt them. In order to solve the problem created by the barriers referred above, the partnership with CBE is helping to give credibility, in terms of the functionality promised, to the biomass supply portion of the solutions.

Sciven’s customers are mainly public entities holding infra-structures with great energy needs and, therefore, expenses. One example of these are municipalities managing public pools. Hotels and industries are the main customers in the private sector. Currently, Sciven has around 20 permanent clients. As for future plans, Sciven aims to scale further in two ways: providing solutions not only for individual consumers but also for energy communities such as industrial parks, and to reach different clients, either in type of activity or geographically.

3.6.2 Timeline

Figure 7: Timeline - Sciven

3.6.3 Main characteristics

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Sciven innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Study research work, observation, and discussion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To gain practical viability and feasibility understanding of energy consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - University of Coimbra (Mechanical Engineering Department)
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Win a contest for entrepreneurship ideas and integration in an acceleration program - Engaging experienced teachers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To set up a business plan and technology development - To capitalize on the academical ecosystem 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Arrisca Coimbra (contest organisation) - COTEC Portugal (training organisation) - Professors at the University of Coimbra
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - establishment of the company - apply for support with R&D projects. - Integrate into a business community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To prepare technological demonstration and financial plan covering the next 3 years - To learn good practices from existing companies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Professors at the University of Coimbra - Incubator
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Production of prototype for domestic use - Strategic decision to scale up the solution and integrate biomass use - Development of own line of biomass-fueled boilers and network building 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To frame the value proposition for accessing the market - To continuously reassess and adapt the solution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - biomass-fuelled boilers manufacturer - Biomass Centre for Energy - Directorate-General of Energy and Geology - Incubator
	Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Product Launch and first clients - Provide the complete energy service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To generate income - To take the responsibility of producing biomass-fueled boilers and their maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - N/A
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - participation in projects, conferences, fairs and network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To convince sceptical consumers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Company network and external collaborators - University of Coimbra - Biomass Centre for Energy - Incubator
	Embedding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Permanent clients - Catering individual consumers and larger energy communities - On-going 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To produce and widespread services - To build trust and credibility - To diversify end-users - To ensure sustainable biomass supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public entities and private industries - Biomass Centre for Energy

Table 7: Overview of characteristics - Sciven

3.7 Straws from natural wheat stems by Staramaki – Greece

Company profile information

Staramaki is a social cooperative, created in 2019, which grasps all the benefits of the social economy. This cooperative has a strong social and environmental purpose which, among others, focuses on labour and social inclusion. Staramaki utilises by-products of wheat cultivation and produces a viable alternative to plastic straws, as well as packaging material - carrying cases for the straws made of reed stems. This cooperative creates job opportunities and, in this way, contributes towards the local and regional development of Kilkis. At the moment, 10 people are working full time and the cooperative has a turnover of €100.000.

Contact profile information

Stefanos Kamperis is an electrical engineer with a master's degree in Product Innovation and Development. He worked as a consultant and R&D manager for Greek and Japanese manufacturing and construction companies. After a collapse in the construction industry in Greece due to an economic crisis, 15 years ago, he decided to move to the rural area of Kilkis and focus on the social economy. As a response to the refugee crisis happening in Greece, he worked towards placing refugees in houses in 2014 preventing them from staying in camps. This was the beginning of what became later the social cooperative Staramaki.

3.7.1 Description of the innovation process

3.7.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial idea

Stefanos and his team after their response to the refugee crisis sought ways to maintain a sustainable economy in Kilkis. It was observed that people moving to bigger cities led to more and more villages being emptied and rural areas being deserted. For the economic development in these areas, unsustainable economic ventures like gold extraction plants seemed to be a solution and the state along with private companies pursued this option but they encountered many barriers from the local population, who in turn managed to stop the creation of these gold mines. Alongside these developments, Stefanos and his team focused on finding an alternative, sustainable solution and this is the point where Staramaki came to the fore. In Greece, drinking cold coffee with a straw is an everyday habit and with the European legislation banning single-use plastics and thus plastic straws, Staramaki offered a relevant, relatable, and viable alternative drinking straw.

The first barrier that Staramaki faced was the infancy of the social economy scheme in Greece and the lack of available funding from the Greek state. In addition, there was no available technology for the production/process of drinking straws made of wheat - as this is a rather novel idea and underdeveloped at this time. Finally, Staramaki had to work with local farmers whose agricultural practices were not sustainable, as is the case for Greece in general, which presented a barrier in the large picture of the coop's sustainability.

Some of the expected benefits of Staramaki were social inclusion, the financial revival of the area, and the introduction in the market of a viable alternative to plastic drinking straws. In addition, Staramaki, as a social enterprise, is equally managed by its members who are all paid the same rate. This working ethic contributes towards a change in how we perceive business and the value of work in general.

Inspiration

During 2018 and 2019, when the idea of Staramaki was shaped, a key actor that played an important role was the Kilkis Agricultural Association who confirmed that there were indeed enough local resources for Staramaki to be successful in this sense. In addition, another significant factor to get things moving was the initial funding it received

from an international organisation based in the UK. In the beginning, three people were involved in Staramaki, contributing equally, driving around Kilkis, searching for equipment, potentially available land, sterilisation methods for the straws and everything else needed for the initiation of Staramaki.

Staramaki capitalised on the precedent of excellent performance of the legal entity during the refugee crisis and previous activity. If this project had not succeeded, as Stefanos described, then Staramaki might not have been feasible. Also, the legislation about plastic straws, the availability of wheat in the area along with the bond and trust amongst the people working together led to the desire to proceed to another venture, the creation of Staramaki.

3.7.1.2 Implementation phase

Planning

After the realisation that Staramaki will be something worth pursuing, the planning phase began. That was towards the end of 2018 and into 2019 when the team found the building which would host the production. The first harvest was done, and the idea was presented to the world through the creation and upload of attractive and relatable videos on social media. The key actors in this phase were the same who were initially involved and mentioned earlier as well as the items that Staramaki was able to capitalise on (favourable legislation, wheat availability in the area, etc.).

The biggest challenges that the team had to face was the lack of financing, which has been attributed mainly to Staramaki's legal form being a social enterprise, the lack of relevant technology and guidance, as the idea and the processes its production entails are innovative and not developed, and also the lack of support from the Greek state.

Development

The development activities started in 2019. The most important milestones during the development phase were when:

1. The right variety of wheat was found - the main wheat variety cultivated in the area was more than suitable for drinking straw (Staramaki is made from the bottom part of the wheat - the stem - which is a by-product of the wheat harvest.).
2. They finalised the concept (choosing the name, the people involved).
3. The right equipment was found, to at least begin processing and production.
4. There was proof of concept - the above points as well as the pilot production of the bio-product proved that the idea was indeed viable and relevant and something to be further developed and with potential for success.
5. A social media diffusion succeeded in spreading the word around for Staramaki and their innovative bio-based solution - the videos went viral very quickly, they were re-posted, local and regional media took up and reported on the story. This further reinforced the team as it preempted that the public is interested in their product and showed potential for a future market.
6. They received the initial funding (August 2019) which meant that they could actually move from pilot to realisation - albeit small scale in the beginning.

One important challenge during the development of Staramaki was firstly the non-existence of standards for bio-based drinking straws - i.e., there was a knowledge gap which the team had to fill in themselves. For this reason, the team decided to undertake research on existing bibliography on treatment of organic biomass. One thing that they were able to capitalise on during this phase was the availability of equipment to treat a food contact related organic product.

Realisation

The first product launch was made in Kilkis in late 2019 - January 2020 at a local level and on a small scale. The most significant steps that Stefanos recognises at this phase are the fact they finally had some financing and, even more importantly, the people themselves who were involved in the initiative. It seems that Stefanos places great importance on the people that the team is composed of, and claims that it would have been very different if it wasn't for them specifically and the team they had been established.

The advantages that Staramaki offers are grouped into three pillars of action: decreasing plastic pollution, reducing rural depopulation, and using regenerative agriculture to eradicate desertification effects.

Comparing the first idea, the old days, of Staramaki with the product now, Stefanos mentioned that the straw is the same but the way of cutting, sterilising, and packaging it has improved. Regarding the general goal and initial idea of Staramaki, what has not been achieved yet is:

1. Incorporating a social housing aspect in the initiative. They were not able yet to have so much profit to provide jobs that will also get people into homes.
2. Follow a more circular model than the one they already do. They are not using the by-product from the main wheat cultivation of the area, as they had initially planned. They cultivate their own wheat.

Stefanos is very keen on pursuing the above and making sure that they are achieved soon.

Staramaki is not patented. As Stefanos described, wheat straws are not a novelty as they were being used even in Ancient Greece and as such they do not deserve to be intellectually protected. Ideally, Staramaki would like to share their know-how with like-minded cooperatives that are focused on and share the same social values.

3.7.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

The diffusion of Staramaki took place from the end of 2019 - the beginning of 2020 via a small video on social media (Facebook) where they managed to go viral, for free and quite quickly. This video was willingly shared by a lot of people and reached 3 million views within a short period of time. The key to success was that everybody could understand what it is and the problem that it was trying to solve - it was relatable both because of the prevalence of drinking straws in the greek culture and beyond, and also because of the timing as single-use plastics had already gained their bad name - there was momentum, the idea was very relevant and it offered an easy, viable solution. This video also drew the attention of various media, newspapers, and reporters who reached out to the team to learn more about the cooperative and their innovative initiative. It was through this publicity that Vichy and L'oreal - big players in the global economy - placed an order for straws, right before the covid pandemic; major market brands got involved.

The challenge during the diffusion phase was the high price of the product and the fact that people did not grasp the interplay between the environmental and social benefits of Staramaki. In addition, Covid-19, on a global scale, stopped and reduced environmental concerns. Because of this, in the Horeca industry the single-wrapping of straws was reintroduced and imposed which created a big challenge for Staramaki as they had to individually wrap each straw in a sustainable manner - this was both time and cost intensive.

The educative nature of what Staramaki does, caring for the future among others, was an important key to capitalise on in this phase.

Embedding

One factor that favoured the adoption of the proposed solution, Staramaki, was that people did not respond well to the alternatives of plastic drinking straws available in the market, i.e., paper straws. Staramaki covers the user experience, promotes locality, has a social aspect leading its goal and it is the first mover in the market. In addition, the financial support of Nestle, which was given in 2021, was crucial for the adoption of Staramaki.

The barrier after the product was placed in the market was the price competition with other alternatives - it did not compete well, as the technological infancy made it expensive to produce. To overcome this problem, Staramaki, with its partnership with Nestle, invested in equipment and better agricultural practices. At this point, the team realised that they would be better off cultivating their own wheat and harvesting its stem, while providing the flower to other farmers and industries. The initial idea was to use the by-product of local production, but for this to happen the harvest must be done manually as the harvesting machinery essentially destroys the stem making it unusable for the purposes that Staramaki utilizes it. Moving away from the initial idea also meant that Staramaki became less circular than anticipated. However, the team saw no other viable way as the farmers were not interested in giving their farms to the team to harvest manually, they preferred the conventional methods that mechanical harvesting provides.

By expanding production, the team aims at enhancing automation and making the production faster, easier, and cheaper.

Regarding future barriers, political and financial instability in the wider area may result in reduction of the purchasing power of buyers, both retail and consumers.

During the product launch, Staramaki had a lot of small customers, hundreds, that wanted to test the product. With Covid-19 the demand was reduced. Afterwards, Staramaki made a pilot project with 100 thousand straws for a Vichy deal and 1 million for Nestle. Around Greece, Staramaki has 17 points of reselling, mostly cooperatives with some small exceptions. Staramaki is not yet placed in supermarkets because of its not competitive price.

Staramaki is not yet mainstream. For it to become mainstream, it needs to stop being an innovation, according to Stefanos. The point when more companies create the product with the same standards and the same social philosophy will make the product more established in the market.

The most crucial future plan is to automate more, scale up with machines and workforce and reach a capacity of 25 million straws per year (i.e., 3 shifts per day). As a next step, Stefanos and his team would like to either replicate production in another location or expand the size of the agricultural site where the production plant is currently located.

3.7.2 Timeline

Figure 8: Timeline - Staramaki

3.7.3 Main characteristics

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Staramaki innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Response to socio-economic patterns and EU single-use plastics legislation - Search for a sustainable and inclusive development opportunity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of available funding - Lack of technology and guidance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local farmers
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local resources assessment - Operational research - Creation of Staramaki 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To obtain initial funding - To emphasize the dynamic of previous project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kilkis Agricultural Association - International organization
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finding the production location - Launch first harvest - Communication activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of guidance - To take advantage of the project vision reaching broader audience. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - N/A
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identification of suitable wheat variety, processing and production - Concept design and significant outreach - Proof of concept initial funding - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Non-existence of standards - To explore existing references - To validate the idea's viability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media audience - International organization -
	Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - First product launch - Improved processing techniques - Looking to share know-how 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To emphasize a reliable team - To benefit from financial support - The social housing aspect and full circular model remains limited 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community of Kilkis
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotional video - Receiving - Involvement of big market brands 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To communicate clearly and be widely shared - To adapt new packing requirement - Product pricing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social media Audience and reporters - Vichy and L'Oreal
	Embedding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consumer awareness to plastic uses - Investment for practice efficiency - Reselling and expanding production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To automate more and generalize the solution - Product pricing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nestle - Vichy

Table 8: Overview of characteristics - Staramaki

3.8 Algae production in wastewater by Algen – Slovenia

Company profile information

Algen is a micro-SME established in 2010, specialized in the development & system integration of the algae technology systems, providing consulting, algal cultivation, wastewater treatment and engineering services. R&D is currently focused on the cultivation of algae on waste streams (wastewater from different industries, digestate, side-streams from food and drink production), simultaneously treating the water by the algae-bacterial process for recycling of nutrients and CO₂ and producing the algal biomass for various valorisations, from valuable extracts to fertilisers.

Algen has been responsible for the R&D of algal wastewater treatment systems and algal biomass production in the scope of several European projects, including the anaerobic digestate from biogas plants (AlgaeBioGas, Saltgae), wastewater from the slaughterhouse (Water2Return) and fruit & vegetables processing industries (LIFE AlgaeCan). Currently, Algen is a partner in many national (lactic acid fermentation for enrichment of the microalgae biomass with new nutrients, cosmetics, animal feed, wastewater treatment, national spirulina production) and international projects, most recently Horizon Europe BioRural (BioRural.eu; Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas), Cronus (Capture and reuse of biogenic gases for negative-emission – sustainable), Locality (Nature-positive algae-based food, agriculture, aquaculture and textile products made in North and Baltic Sea ecosystems), and FuelPhoria (Accelerating the sustainable production of advanced biofuels and RFNBOs - from feedstock to end-use). Algen is also a part of COST action “Applications for zoospore parasites in aquatic systems” for monitoring and preventing infections in large-scale algal production systems.

The algal demonstration centre for the AlgaeBioGas project was established in 2014 and subsequently used for the Saltgae project as well as for the education and rising awareness. Another demonstration centre, Algae Park, was established together with the Biotechnical faculty (University of Ljubljana, Slovenia) in the scope of Water2Return project. Algal systems like various raceway ponds, algal biofilms, bioreactors and harvesting systems are being developed in the Algae Park. Most projects are focused to the circular economy approach for the recycling of nutrients (and energy) from wastewaters, which are then injected back into the agricultural system as new raw materials or used as a secondary materials/compound for agricultural biostimulants, biomaterials, animal feed, coatings, cosmetics, pharmacy, etc.

Algen has designed, engineered, and built several high-grade *Spirulina* production facilities (600 m² in Ljubljana & 300 m² in Kranj, Slovenia, 1000 m² in Grosseto, Italy,) for producing super high-quality food-grade algae and cooperates with many international academic and commercial institutions and occasionally hosts algal-technology educational activities. It is an active member of EABA, European Algae Biomass Association, especially in the wastewater/digestate treatment and industry sector.

Contact profile information

Robert Reinhardt is a CEO of Algen. He graduated from University of Ljubljana in 1983. He has more than 15 years of experience in algal cultivation, production and wastewater treatment, algal pond design and installation. From 1988 to 2001 he was a founding partner, CTO and CEO in one of the largest Slovenian software development and system integration companies (80 employees). The company was merged into a European system integration group. Since that time, he was acting as a business angel and consultant in various operations, Algen is the last on-going one. As the CEO of Algen, he was leading the work under Albaqua Cornet project and under AlgaDisk FP7 RSME project. He coordinated AlgaeBioGas project and was the technical manager for Saltgae project (Horizon 2020) as well as lead coordinator and developer for 0.5 ha high grade Spirulina production facility in Italy and 300 & 600 m² facilities in Slovenia, 400 m² algal pond in Seville, Spain (Water2Return, H2020), and algal mixotrophic/heterotrophic pilot installation in LIFE AlgaeCan project. Currently he's working on design and installation of algal systems for several Horizon Europe projects, including functional prototype for biogenic gas capture and reuse (Cronus), and 1000 m² demo installation (FuelPhoria) in Greece. He is also a member of COST ParAqua action and legal issues partner in Horizon Europe Locality project.

3.8.1 Description of the innovation process

3.8.1.1 Initiation phase

Initial idea

The idea is very natural: biogas is sometimes used for energy reuse of agricultural and other waste and sometimes it is used as a renewable energy source based on energy crops. In all such cases the main process that goes on is fundamentally circular: Crops → Biomass → Biogas → Energy use (motor) → CO₂ (recycled to crops via atmosphere), Digestate (used as fertilizer for crops). There are, however, many practical problems: liquid digestate is very dilute, this causes logistic problems (storage, transportation) and agrotechnical problems (flushing the soil nutrient holding capacity, leaching of nutrients to underground). Biogas digestate is thus frequently separated to solid phase that is used as conventional fertilizer, and liquid phase that is frequently treated as wastewater.

Additional problems emerge from the fact that biogas feedstock is frequently brought-in from different locations and return of fertilizers to the same area is simply not possible. Currently there is a surplus of nitrogen because it comes not only from local sources (agro-waste), but also from the imported food and feed (like soy for agriculture) from outside of Europe. This (with other reasons) is manifested in nitrogen limited zones, where excess fertilization with nitrogen is simply forbidden as the inflow of nitrogen rich materials into the geographic area has been too high (for too long time). EU is working on preventing excessive nitrogen application to the agricultural fields, adding to the problematic of digestate utilisation for fertilisation of soil.

Biogas operators thus have problems using biogas digestate as a fertilizer. Some pay for such use; some invent other ways to eliminate the digestate problem. Biogas anaerobic digestion is primarily a technology for waste treatment and secondarily a source of renewable energy. The waste is organic from various sources, but mostly from the agriculture and wastewater treatment. Biogas plants business operation is mostly based on incentives. The result is 2000+ and 8000+ biogas plants running on agricultural waste in Italy and Germany, respectively. In contrast, France and Spain currently don't have any agro-waste fed biogas plants, running mostly on wastewater sludge. The third type of biogas plants is based on landfill waste.

Biomethane has a crucial role in the initiative RePower Europe, because it can be fed to the existing gas grid. The initiative has a target of producing 39 billion m³ per year by 2030. Biogas plants play an important role in biomethane production, which means their involvement in production will rise and with it the level of digestate.

So, fundamental challenge is what to do with the excess nitrogen. There are several options how to convert ammonium in the digestate:

- (1) Acquisition of ammonium and utilisation of its gaseous phase,
- (2) Nitrification to nitrate, which is used as a nutrient for biomass production),
- (3) Denitrification for N₂ production, which is released into air. The last option is waste of energy that was used for nitrogen fixation.

The first two options represent recycling and maybe even return of the produced biomass/fertiliser to the starting point (the origin place of food/feed).

It was envisioned a solution by growing algae in the liquid phase of the biogas digestate to treat it to acceptable levels for the re-use or safe release to the environment. This approach enables recycling of energy, nitrogen, and the rest of the nutrients. Produced algal biomass can be used as biogas feedstock (for biogas upgrade) and biofertilisers or used for a higher value product, like feed, bioplastics, bio-stimulants, bio-pesticides or even for extraction of valuable substances in biorefinery.

The idea for this solution emerged from discussions with many biogas operators and listening to their digestate problems. Knowing about algae cultivation the availability of nutrient rich liquid was a natural way to bring in algae.

Inspiration

Initial inspiration stemmed from the wish for more innovative agricultural practice. As with most ideas, the idea alone seemed appealing to many (once the essentials of algal technology explained), especially as it was not very clear what kind of obstacles must be overcome and the economic feasibility was not very clear. The idea was interesting to many different fields of research and institutions. From wastewater treatment operators to microbial processes developers and agriculturists, they were all keen to try working with algae. Although first focus was biofuel from algae (already in 2007), it soon became clear that this kind of valorisation wasn't ready for the market by far, mostly because of the non-competitive prices. Thus, the most important breakthrough was when we managed to engage a biogas operator in our vicinity to join us in preparing a project proposal.

Before agreeing to build a demonstration centre at the biogas plant, an assessment of the suitability of using biogas digestate as a substrate for algae growth was performed. This sufficed to further collaboration on AlgaeBioGas (ABG) technology. Main inspiration was the problematics with the liquid anaerobic digestate and its challenge in utilisation or removal that was already recognized by experts (including biogas plants' managers). They knew that algae are very efficient in treating a nutrient-rich waste substrates from previous project on wastewater treatment in paper industry. They were also involved in the studies of utilisation of treated liquid digestate for aquaponics at the University of Ljubljana.

After the ABG demo centre was built, AlgaeBioGas.eu became the flagship project that enabled getting important contacts and invitations to events. On top of building our reputation in algae sector, presentations on biogas events, like ACI (The Future of Biogas) or final event of the Microgate project, resulting in interest from biogas operators, which shared with us their problematics. The technology proved to be interesting also for the food-grade spirulina production (with pure mineral nutrients, not waste streams).

3.8.1.2 Implementation phase

Planning

After an initial idea of circular utilisation of agricultural fields for biogas, biofuel and ethanol feedstock, and food in 2007, all calculations were made for the operation and valorisation. While the initial idea wasn't realised, the calculations and modelling came in handy when discussing the approach to other possible collaborators. They soon began to work with the Agricultural department in the Biotechnical faculty of the University of Ljubljana and started to apply for funding. They started to study the liquid phase of anaerobic digestate and utilisation of algae for its treatment and stabilisation of nutrients. By that time, they already had some experience with the algae treatment of wastewater from paper industry. The work eventually led to other institutions and finally to the Ljubljana biogas plant Koto. They connected together with the University and got the funding from Eco-Innovation call. At the same time, studies of the possible algae utilisation in biogas plant were performed at the University.

Luckily, they had a forward-looking management in the project partner (biogas plant) and were aware that the solution may not be fully applicable in their case (due to space restrictions), but they were curious enough to try. Planning of the project was conventional, like for all EU projects. They had a small and very efficient project consortium with a local very motivated team and were granted the Eco-innovation project AlgaeBioGas (ABG). The project proposal was less than perfect but had a reviewer who liked our idea enough to support it despite some deficiencies that were cleared in the negotiation stage.

Development

Real development started with designing and construction of first raceway pond systems for a spirulina production in Ljubljana. After the installation, parameters for algal cultivation in large scale ponds were studied and gathered also in parallel experience on wastewater treatment with algae on other projects. Both lines of experience were joined in ABG project.

Development proceeded smoothly, some of the necessary activities were outsourced, but it turned out the two consortium partners were nicely complementary: there was sufficient technical and construction support and expertise at the biogas operator (for their other activities) that greatly complemented Algen domain knowledge

and made the design and implementation possible. Outside expert help was selected naturally from the existing partnering organizations.

The initial ABG project had a goal to treat the digestate and return the produced algae back to the operation as a feedstock for biogas production. After the end of ABG project, the demo algae system was utilised in much bigger EU Horizon 2020 project Saltgae, where certain work was performed also to upgrade the algae production and harvesting for valorisation of biomass for higher-value products, which would make the whole system more appealing to the potential end users. Automatic control and sensor systems for optimised operation was developed as well. The algal systems were further developed for higher efficiency in other demos (for example in Seville, Spain in the scope of Water2Return.eu project) as well as studied for specific products like biofertilisers and biostimulants with University of Ljubljana.

Realisation

The ABG technology innovation was first delivered during the ABG project (2013-2016). The funded project already included the activity of market replication of the technology, so they were forced early to do the business planning, market analysis, even some pre-sales activity. This was perhaps a bit earlier than expected, but it turned to be just right. The project called to build a demonstration centre that have been used to bring potential customers to the site and even test their materials as substrates. Thus, the project dissemination activity brought in a stream of inquiries and visit to the demonstration centre.

Within the project we brought the technology to a level ripe for potential early adopters. Due to complexity of the project, we were not able to do a straightforward quotation with guaranteed performance and well-defined budget, but we were ready to prepare proposals for a two-stage project: a feasibility study followed by an initial design and the implementation stage based on the measured performance from the first stage. They never claimed to be overconfident with any of the customers and this proved to be a distinguishing factor: several customers told post-festum that they talked to many over-confident providers who were not aware of implementation problems or that have solved the problems at least once.

Out of the stream of potential customers a deal has been concluded that was initially modelled to be a second implementation of the technology, but within the requirement and designed stage they moved away from the basic ABG technology and implemented a spirulina farm that was disconnected from the biogas plant (of the same operator). This was a natural development based on the customer and market requirements. Even though the technology was not replicated it was clear that the customer would never come to us without the ABG technology, and they would have never selected us for the implementation if the perfectly working biogas demonstration centre have not been showed.

Time between the start of the idea and implementation of the installation #2 was around 4 years.

Algen is still waiting for the implementation #3. We are in contact with many potential customers that are in the process of closing the financial construction of such a project. Recently, Algen have been awarded a feasibility study that might result in design and installation of algal system in Italy. Such as in a new Horizon Europe projects including design and installation of algal systems fed with digestate and valorisation plan for algal biomass.

3.8.1.3 Diffusion phase

Dissemination

The product (ABG technology) and service (design, installation, optimisation) were first launched during the ABG project (2013-2016). Once the demonstration site was finished and it became obvious that it is working, people began to visit it. A website has been created, AlgaeBioGas.eu, and many people have found the innovation through it. In addition, they attended various events around Europe, from biogas operators to algae researchers and wastewater treatment operators.

Algen became connected with the known experts on the field, for example Aqualia and University of Almeria (Spain). Algen was co-founders of EABA (European Algae Biomass Association) in 2009. Also, they had an invited presentation on IWA event (International Water Association), where they connected with Italian researchers in the field. Such as with many Italian biogas plant's operators because of the dissemination on their events.

After seeing the ABG technology demo centre in Ljubljana, they were offered a job to build an installation for food-grade spirulina production in Italy (2015), which is still operational. Algen became a part of project with Wageningen University (The Netherlands), which are one of the most known experts of algae. Based on the dissemination activities we have gained a reputation as the expert company for algae and biogas in EU which means that they are frequently contacted for partnership by providers that are quite capable of implementing a project themselves.

There exists a partial implementation of similar technologies, but no flagship big second implementation yet. It is quite likely that we will participate in any such project at least as a consultant if not as a system integrator. Currently, we are a part of the consortia for capture and reuse of biogenic gases (Horizon Europe CRONUS) and sustainable production of advanced biofuels (Horizon Europe FuelPhoria), one of the technologies being ABG, and a consortium for demonstrating Nature-positive algae-based products made in North and Baltic Sea ecosystems (Horizon Europe LOCALITY).

Embedding

To date, algae-based technologies haven't fully permeated mainstream practices, with the potential exception of spirulina farming for food purposes. However, the framework established by the ABG technology finds its niche across several nutrient and energy recovery platforms. Even though the integration presently remains bespoke, there's a strong impetus towards standardization. The aspiration is that through the productization of these techniques, they can drive down costs and democratize access to these technologies. In line with this vision, Algen is actively involved in preliminary stages of projects aimed at achieving this objective.

3.8.2 Timeline

Figure 9: Timeline – Algen

3.8.3 Main characteristics

The table below gives an overview of the actions carried out, their progress, the players involved, the difficulties encountered, and the support received in the Algen innovation process.

Innovation phase		Activities and key improvements	Challenges and key issues	Key actors involved
Initiation phase	Initial idea	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Observation of the biogas production cycle - Envisaging algae cultivation as a solution 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biogas operators face difficulties in deploying digestate as a fertilizer (logistic, regulatory restrictions...) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biogas operators - RePower Europe initiative

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementations relies on incentives. - Discussions of needs with multiple biogas operators 	
	Inspiration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interest from various sector and event participation - Collaboration for a project proposal with a biogas operator - Viability assessment - Establishment the AlgaeBioGas project and demonstration center 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Building experience on previous project and studies - To showcase the innovation potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biogas operator - University of Ljubljana
Implementation phase	Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Modelling operation and valorisation - New collaborator, apply for funding and grant - Start of a study 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biogas plant had space limitations, making full application of the solution uncertain - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agricultural department in the Biotechnical faculty of the University of Ljubljana - Biogas operator - Funding entity - Project proposal reviewer
	Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishment of a first raceway pond systems for a spirulina production - Further technology experiment and product development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To enhance the complementarity expertise - To develop R&D of the solution via EU project or other demo 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - External expert support - Biogas operator - University of Ljubljana
	Realisation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Replicability, business planning, market analysis, some pre-sales activity - ABG project dissemination - Second implementation of the technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Elevated the technology to early adopters - Build trust to distinguish from competitors - Two-stage consultancy approach to project proposals: a feasibility study followed by an initial design and implementation stage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential customers
Diffusion phase	Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website creation for the ABG technology - Participation in events, projects and integrate network of experts - Demo center visits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involved in European Algae Biomass Association (co-founder) - Enhancing Algen's reputation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aqualia - University of Almeria - EABA - Wageningen University
	Embedding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ABG technology finds its niche. - To get the technology mainstream (on-going) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardization and productization of the techniques 	N/A

Table 9: Overview of characteristics - Algen

4 Discussion

The outcomes of this research have provided insight into the innovation process of 8 European bioeconomy success stories. However, the results should be interpreted, with caution due to the limitation of the investigation, and this section is intended to provide a reflection on the research potential consequences as well as the implications of the lesson learnt. The assessment of the success stories innovation processes is derived from diverse bioeconomy themes and provides in each case a learning story. Each learning story emphasis the entrepreneurial journey as an example of good practice to be followed or to be inspired from. It indicates key items such as the involvement of local and regional stakeholders but also underlines activities, challenges and factors of success in accessing the market.

Therefore, the assessed success stories demonstrate a correlation between the success of bioeconomy initiatives and the implication of fostering collaborations, therefore having a knowledge exchange and facilitation network. Notably, the data suggests that the transition to a circular bioeconomy in Europe is reliant on regional expertise that is balanced between traditional knowledge and innovative attempts. This hands-on approach, involving close collaboration with community stakeholders, enables traditional knowledge and innovations to be effectively exploited. This means that the transition to sustainable rural development and it’s scaling up, in terms of circular and biobased initiatives, requires research and the testing of pilot schemes.

In the context of accelerating circular and bio-based solutions in rural areas, a discernible pattern emerges from the success stories analysed: initiatives that flourish tend to be faithfully linked to their value chain and the handling of raw materials. The success stories suggests that local resource management plays an integral part in the design of bioeconomy initiatives, as initial ideas are fully grounded and developed on regional needs and opportunities. Indeed, the 8 BioRural success stories showcase a bottom-up strategy, providing customized solutions alongside practical business prospects.

In the rural settings, the success stories are individually targeting global challenges at the local level by leveraging sustainable resources. Therefore, the transition from petroleum-based to biobased solutions paves the way for rural development and the elaboration of sustainable value chains, namely by addressing a niche market or a specific segment with distinct needs. The biobased markets typically have less competition and can offer worthwhile opportunities for businesses that effectively accommodate to these specialized demands.

Figure 10: Success stories noteworthy elements - BIORURAL

Upon analysing the several innovation processes, common recurring elements emerge, outlining noteworthy elements that can be taken into account to achieve successful business models. Thus, 6 features have been identified as common and can be characterised as follows:

Genuine and Friendly Biomass Management: It refers to the initial approach of biomass utilization, which is rooted in sustainable practices. In this sense, the success story authenticity doesn't simply relate to the technological innovation or process applied but extends to the deeper environmental and social attributes associated with the biomass management. The practices are authentic, free from superficial or misleading attribute, and naturally underscores a harmonious and beneficial relationship with both the environment and the society. It values practices that minimize environmental harm, promote sustainable growth, and ensure equitable resource distribution, thus amplifying the value and credibility of bioeconomy in a comprehensive manner.

Niche Market and Value Chain Alignment: It refers to the landscape of sustainable business innovation where, discerning gaps or exploring needs in the larger market and tailoring their offerings accordingly is a strategic move. By focusing on these niche areas, companies avoid direct competition and saturated markets. Instead, they can craft solutions, products, or services, which are inherently more tailored and potentially more valuable to the target audience. Furthermore, the particularly disruptive aspect of this tackling a niche market is its ability to reshape or realign established value chains. It provides a strategic entry point to market differentiation and growth, while also promoting innovative shifts in the broader business ecosystem.

Practical and Tailor-made Solutions: It refers to the fact that biobased and circular applications are grounded, easy to integrate, and address actual problems or needs. Tailor-made solutions increase the relevance of the product or service, ensuring that the innovation finds a more receptive audience. Furthermore, personalized solutions cultivate a deeper sense of connection and trust between the company and its clientele. This way, considering practical and tailor-made solutions is about laying the foundation for enduring business relationships. In the bioeconomy success stories context, gaining traction is often linked through the ability to fine-tune the solution to fit the unique requirements or preferences for adoption.

Adaptive and Sustainable Growth Strategy: It refers to the economic, social, and environmental as determinant in a biobased innovation survival and prosperity. The paradigm of the companies' resilience and growth are those that have encompasses a proactive monitoring of global and local trends, anticipating shifts, and recalibrating business models accordingly. For instance, a bioeconomy domain innovation might modify its product, process, or portfolio in response to new environmental regulations or adjust its supply chain based on evolving socio-economic scenarios. Furthermore, an adaptive and sustainable growth strategy also plays a pivotal role in demonstrating a commitment to long-term growth rather than short-term gain. It builds reputation and showcase the company favourably in the community. This approach is a forward-looking vision, intended to positively shape the future and in parallel ensuring to remain relevant in an ever-shifting landscape.

Research Process and Experimental Pilots: It refers to the importance of empirical validation as a fundamental development step that cannot be understated. Hereby, for businesses operating within the bioeconomy sector, the deployment of research-driven and experimental pilots has emerged as a cardinal principle in their innovation processes. Rather than considering theoretical assumptions or general market trends, conducting experimental pilots represent a pillar in the decision-making process and in the innovation's market success. Therefore, enhancing a research environments where new ideas can be discussed, executed, assessed provide a playground for innovation. In addition, this approach not only ensure the innovation robustness but reinforce credibility as industry pioneers.

Collaboration with local stakeholders: It refers to the involvement of an innovation ecosystem as a foundational principle for implementing innovation. Such collaborations result primarily in knowledge sharing or co-development of solutions but these synergies can also be structuring in fostering collective growth, obtaining infrastructure, accessing technological, legislative or financing expertise, and market insights that might otherwise remain inaccessible. Support organizations are catalyst for growth by acting as bridges, connecting to vital resources, thereby conditioning innovation. This local synergy ensures sustainable and community-aligned growth, while providing continuous feedback. Ultimately, local collaboration isn't just a strategic choice; it's a holistic consideration of the innovation credibility by fostering collective prosperity and relevance.

Accordingly, through the BIORURAL pioneering success stories, a panorama of empirical evidence is presented, and several attributes emerge that can be considered as success factors for these initiatives. For future ventures in this field, the detailed attributes of BIORURAL success stories can serve as a lighthouse, ensuring that progress meets the needs and aspirations of local and global communities.

In terms of possible replicability and scalability, these purpose-driven strategies generally face less competition, enabling companies to respond effectively to specific demands and drive sustainable growth. This convergence requires a three-dimensional balance: economic, environmental, and social. Through good practices in the bioeconomy domain, companies are called upon to promote efficient biomass uses, integrating circular solutions for a harmonious and innovative rural areas. Therefore, reflecting that the success stories innovation processes are not only framed by the function of a new product or process, but by a harmonious combination of ecological problem-solving, market positioning, long-term commitment, and deep-rooted collaboration. The underlying pattern is clear: transparent integration of value chains, raw material management and the distinctive need of the region is paramount.

5 Conclusion

The examination of the bioeconomy success stories provide an understanding of the current rural bioeconomy pathway of innovation within the BIORURAL project. The seven stages of the innovation spiral serve as a testament to the nature of each innovation processes, emphasizing structured progression and involving diverse stakeholders and intricate sequences. This methodology, while robust, is not exhaustive as the uniqueness of each story relies on varying perspectives and expertise.

As an outcome, this document crosses inside each innovation process the notable elements that have been bordered during the research process and which upon priorities, opportunities, and synergies can be reflected. Within the overall investigation, it appears that each success story has its own organizational specificities but remains focus on similar activities. For instance, the cases appeared to emphasis good collaboration with local industry players and to tailormade the innovative solution according to economic, social or environmental requirements. Similarly, with the involvement of support organization the ability to quantify and test a first experimental pilot is generally acquired. As part of the replicability and scalability, the BIORURAL biobased success stories are likely positioned as niche market, transforming existing value chains, and intended to be develop on a larger scale. The success stories, particularly when faced with initial errors or uncertainties, remain practical, looking for customised solutions, yet open to other solutions.

Therefore, by highlighting the pathway that has been followed, it is possible to understand the factors influencing and accelerating the adoption of a innovation in the biobased industry.

The eight case studies accentuate the importance of local roots, the authenticity of the product development that is carried from its unique and meaningful attributes. In conclusion, the BIORURAL success stories, are presented by a promotional video and characterised by a comprehensive breakdown of the innovation process. The assessment set up a cooperation framework in which we have practical example of successful entrepreneurship achievements and attempts. Ultimately, the assess biobased and circular success stories illustrate a holistic approach learning, combining technological innovation and adaptative growth strategy.

BIORURAL success stories video (YouTube): <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCysejLMm1uufYXxyZMePewg>

6 Annexes

6.1 Guideline WP2 – T2.3

Accelerating circular bio-based solutions integration in European rural areas

T2.3 Guidelines

Innovation processes of selected success stories

Table of contents:

- 1) Description of the action
- 2) About the Interview
 - About the interview procedure
 - The interview scheme
- 3) About the Video-based material
 - About the video procedure
 - The video interview scheme

2) biorural.eu

1) Description of the action

The BioRural project has identified 8 success stories and our objective is to determine the success factors of these success stories, their replicability and their scalability. We are looking to produce an analysis of the innovation process, resulting in the following elements:

- The chronology of the innovation process
- The key actors involved
- The challenges faced (technical, socio-economic, environmental aspects...)
- The support received (participation in well-established networks, access to funding, political support...)
- The strategic improvements in relation to the green deal and the bioeconomy

To this purpose, we will conduct interviews with each of the success stories, then the cases will be documented through written documents and video based material. The outcomes will be available in the BioRural toolbox.

Participant Nr.	Selected Success Stories	Related partners	Country
1	Delphy	Delphy	NL
2	NaturePlast	Valorial	FR
3	Pustelnia	IUNG	PL
4	LVM	LLU	LV
5	Aceites Guadalentin & Bioliza	AVEBIOM	ES
6	Sciven	CBE	PT
7	Staramaki	ICO	EL
8	Algen	Algen	SI

2) About the Interview

Good interview questions should be like a conversation with a friend. People usually like to tell their story, especially if you have already established a relationship with them. When you ask questions and listen, you build trust, so keep in mind that it is the person you are talking to who is able to give a convincing story that can be learned from. Therefore, keep in mind that it is up to you to bring out the specificities of each success story.

However, the interview follows the innovation spiral and the findings should be able to characterise 3 stages, namely:

- Initiation phase (initial idea & inspiration)
- Implementation phase (planning, development & implementation)
- Diffusion phase (dissemination & embedding)

The Spiral identifies seven stages in an innovation process, from the initial idea until the embedding stage of the innovation. In each stage in Spiral of Innovations there are different key activities to be performed, actors to be involved and typical pitfalls to be avoided.

About the Interview procedure

Step 1: Get a first contact with your Success story

- Present BioRural and the relevance of WP2
- Identify the main contact who see the big picture and who will represent the success story
- Schedule with them individual a face-to-face (or online) meeting
- Invite them to start their reflections before the interview to ensure the most relevant results

Step 2: Before the interview

- Make sure you have recording material and that it works properly
- Make sure they agree to be recorded (see **Authorization for image and personal data processing**)

Step 3: During the interview

- You must follow the established **Interview Scheme** which is our common red line
- Keep in mind our interview methodology should be considered as semi-structured which means you are also free to react and ask question according to what you consider relevant.

Step 4: After the interview

- Write down your first impressions & personal observations
- Listen the interview you have recorded a second time and make a synthesis following the **Interview Reception Sheet**
- Feel pleased to gather any relevant document to be add
- Share the results to Valorial

The Interview Scheme

Below is the red line of our interviews with the questions related to the results we are looking for.

Regular information

Information about the interviewee

- What's your background and previous experience?
- What circumstances led you to XXX?
- Can you please tell us briefly about your initial and current functions by XXX?

Information about the company

- Company activities presentation and background, date of creation
- Principles of technology in use.
- Current portfolio of solutions/products/services
- Staff nb. and Turnover

1. Initiation Phase

1.1) **Initial Idea:** *Someone has an idea in response to a problem or an opportunity.*

- Describe the initial challenge that was observed and under what circumstances? (Environmental concerns, policy driven innovation, production problems...)
- Who came up with the initial idea of innovation and when?
- What were the challenge and barriers at the beginning?
- What were the expected benefit of the envisaged innovation?

1.2) **Inspiration:** *Others become inspired and form a "warm network" around the initiative.*

- Who were the key actors involved in the development of the idea?
- How did each involved person contribute?
- Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on? (Participation in established networks, access to finance, policy support...)

2. Implementation Phase

2.1) Planning: *The network of initiators organises itself and negotiates space for experimentation.*

- When did you start your planning activities?
- Who were the key actors involved in the planning of the development of the innovation? How did each of them contribute?
- Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on? (Participation in established networks, access to finance, policy support...)
- What were the challenge and barriers in the planning ? Difficulties at planning stage (financial, not the right people at the right time, access to information/knowledge, etc.)

2.2) Development: *The initiators experiment to develop new practices and evidence of their effectiveness.*

- When did you start your development activities?
- Which stages can be recognized in the development of the innovation? When did each stage happen?
- Who were the key actors involved in each stage of the development? How did each of them contribute?
- What were the challenge and barriers in the development of each stage? (Technical, societal demands, policy, financial, legislation, knowledges gaps, human resources...)
- Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on? (Participation in established networks, access to finance, policy support, external factors...)

2.3) Realisation: *The innovation is implemented in full scale*

- When was the innovation delivered?
- What are the most significant steps that led you here? Which stage are you able to recognize that made a difference in term of outcomes?
- What are the advantages that this innovation offers? Old days (first idea) vs. now (finished product in the market)?
- Is the product licensed/parented?

3. Diffusion Phase

3.1) Dissemination: *Other people become interested and implement the innovation.*

- When and how did you launch your product/service?
- How did you manage the diffusion of your solution? What dissemination strategy? (Participation in demonstrations, agricultural fairs, collaboration with more resellers/dealers...)
- Who were the key actors involved in dissemination? How did each of them contribute?
- What were the challenge and barriers in the dissemination?
- Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on?

3.2) Embedding: *The innovation becomes common practice/ is widely accepted and structures/ rules, etc. adapt to the new reality.*

- What factors favored the adoption of the proposed solution? (ease of use, visible results, operator comfort, cheap, availability of technical support...)
- Advantages that this innovation offers? Old days (first idea) vs. now (finished product in the market)?
- What were the barriers after the product was put on the market? How did you solve this? Do you have new one?
- Who are your customers and how many do you currently have? How many do you usually have?
- Is your innovation becoming mainstream? Why?
- What future plans do you have for your biobased solution? to scale further?

Information on lessons learned

- Name the top two or three lessons you learned from your experience?
- What would you say to others who wants to implement a biobased solution in rural areas? What would be your personal recommendations?
- Are there specific stories or anecdotes you can tell us about XXX? Is there anything you would like to highlight regarding your experience at XXX?
- Anything you'd like to add that I haven't asked?

Deadline: 25 February 2023

3) About the Video based material

The video-based material is intended to show the key factors for successful innovation process in rural areas. Strongly related to the interview results, it can be seen has a summary of the previous interviews.

Videos details:

- Duration: Approx. 5 min / Language: Speech in mother tongue / Location: Workplace of the company
- About the editing and the visual identity of the Success Stories videos, please [refer to the DEC plan](#)
- Find [here a playlist with reliable example](#) for our purpose
- Following the specificities of your success story you may have to collect video material with different requirements

It is important to understand what the videos are about. In our case it is meant to inspire and motivate so that the initiatives presented are replicated at EU level. In order to achieve this objective, the focus for this type of video should be the coherence of the visuals and the clarity of the message. The idea is to give information that is easy to memorize while accompanying it with relevant visuals. Get also images that support the speech of the involved people and show the added value of the solution.

About the Video procedure

Step 1: Be prepared

- Write an outline of what you want to show in the video (according to your previous interview results)
- Be aware of the different video production possibilities according to our available funding

- Get in touch with a communication agency

Step 2: Before the filming

- Schedule a day dedicated to the filming with the success story and the communication agency
- Make sure they agree to be filmed (fulfilment of the agreement document)
- Careful! Following the specificities of your success story you may have to collect video material at specific moment of the year!

Step 3: During the filming

- Collect video (+photo) material of the company's environment and working practices.
- Collect a filmed interview following the **Video Interview Scheme**
- Be attentive that background/visual underline what the content explains

Step 4: After the filming

- Translate the speech into English (for subtitles)
- Let the communication agency edit the video
- Send the video to Valorial for review and integration in the toolkit

The Video Interview Scheme

1) *Context and challenge*

Problem/Motivation/Involved actors/partners/Background/previous experience

2) *Action*

First step/Development stage/involved actors/Encountered difficulties/milestones/Received support/Principle of the technology in use

3) *Results and outcomes*

Launching of the innovative product/When and how/Number of current users and prospects/Factors in favor of its adoption/Advantages that this innovation offers/first idea vs. now

4) *Perspective*

What are the next steps/new challenge/continuation/ future plans

Deadline: 15 July 2023

6.2 Template for 'Interview reception sheet'

Interview for success stories following the scheme of the Innovation spiral

The Spiral identifies seven stages in an innovation process, from the initial idea until the embedding stage of the innovation. In each stage in Spiral of Innovations there are different key activities to be performed, actors to be involved and typical pitfalls to be avoided.

COMPANY NAME

Interviewee:

Date of the interview:

Interviewer:

REGULAR INFORMATION

Information about the interviewee

What's your background and previous experience? What circumstances led you to XXX? Can you please tell us briefly about your initial and current functions by XXX?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Information about the company

Company activities presentation and background, date of creation, Principles of technology in use., Current portfolio of solutions/products/services, Staff nb. and Turnover

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

INITIAL PHASE

Initial idea *(Someone has an idea in response to a problem or an opportunity)*

Describe the initial challenge that was observed and under what circumstances? (Environmental concerns, policy driven innovation, production problems...) Who came up with the initial idea of innovation and when? What were the challenge and barriers at the beginning? What were the expected benefit of the envisaged innovation?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Inspiration *(Others become inspired and form a "warm network" around the initiative)*

Who were the key actors involved in the development of the idea? How did each involved person contribute? Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on? (Participation in established networks, access to finance, policy support...)

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

IMPLEMENTATION PHASE

Planning *(The network of initiators organises itself and negotiates space for experimentation)*

When did you start your planning activities? Who were the key actors involved in the planning of the development of the innovation? How did each of them contribute? Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on? (Participation in established networks, access to finance, policy support...) What were the challenge and barriers in the planning? Difficulties at planning stage (financial, not the right people at the right time, access to information/knowledge, etc.)

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Development *(The initiators experiment to develop new practices and evidence of their effectiveness)*

When did you start your development activities? Which stages can be recognized in the development of the innovation? When did each stage happen? Who were the key actors involved in each stage of the development? How did each of them contribute? What were the challenge and barriers in the development of each stage? (Technical, societal demands, policy, financial, legislation, knowledges gaps, human resources...) Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on? (Participation in established networks, access to finance, policy support, external factors...)

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Realisation *(The innovation is implemented in full scale)*

When was the innovation delivered? What are the most significant steps that led you here? Which stage are you able to recognize that made a difference in term of outcomes? What are the advantages that this innovation offers? Old days (first idea) vs. now (finished product in the market)? Is the product licensed/parented?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

DIFFUSION PHASE

Dissemination *(Other people become interested and implement the innovation)*

When and how did you launch your product/service? How did you manage the diffusion of your solution? What dissemination strategy? (Participation in demonstrations, agricultural fairs, collaboration with more resellers/dealers...) Who were the key actors involved in dissemination? How did each of them contribute? What were the challenge and barriers in the dissemination? Are there any items that you were able to capitalise on?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

Embedding *(The innovation becomes common practice/ is widely accepted and structures/ rules, etc. adapt to the new reality)*

What factors favored the adoption of the proposed solution? (ease of use, visible results, operator comfort, cheap, availability of technical support...) Advantages that this innovation offers? Old days (first idea) vs. now (finished product in the market)? What were the barriers after the product was put on the market? How did you solve this? Do you have new one? Who are your customers and how many do you currently have? How many do you usually have Is your innovation becoming mainstream? Why? What future plans do you have for your biobased solution? to scale further?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

INFORMATION ON LESSONS LEARNED

Name the top two or three lessons you learned from your experience? What would you say to others who wants to implement a biobased solution in rural areas? What would be your personal recommendations? Are there specific stories or anecdotes you can tell us about XXX? Is there anything you would like to highlight regarding your experience at XXX? Anything you'd like to add that I haven't asked?

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.

TIMELINE

6.3 Template for ‘Authorization for image and personal data processing’

Authorization for image and personal data processing

I, undersigned (First name, Last name):, hereafter referred to as “*the speaker*”

Belonging to (Organisation name):

authorizes the Biorural project (nr 101072248) and associated project partners, hereafter referred to as “*the organisers*”

ARTICLE 1

To use my image (photographs and/or videos taken by the organisers and/or provided by the speaker to the organisers) and/or my voice, and in particular to record, diffuse, or exploit them, by fixation, reproduction, and/or representation of them in the context of a communication and/or archiving activity, for pedagogical, research, cultural, scientific or historical purposes, on types of media that are known or unknown at this time (including paper, analogical, digital or electronic media), in particular:

- Publication on the organiser’s website,
- Publication on the organisers partner sites,
- Public presentation, presentation of all or part of the website at conferences, events, or symposium related to open and distance learning or the dissemination of academic knowledge,
- Copies on any digital support, in particular DVD, USB key, hard disk, copy on any institutional publication of the organisers (brochure, newspaper, booklet...),
- Copies on other supports than digital media (screen capture prints, etc.) and conversions to other formats (scanning photographs, etc.)

To the express exclusion of:

- Operations outside the context of the communication activities related to the project activities,
- Any use likely to damage reputation or any other medium of pornographic, racist, xenophobic character or any other prejudicial exploitation.

The speaker also allows the organisers to communicate to any partner of the event, any photograph or video on any type of support (in particular paper, analogic, digital or electronic). This authorization is granted to the organisers for the whole world. It takes effect on the date of its signature by the speaker and is granted for the duration necessary for the communication and archiving operation. It is conferred free of charge and without compensation. The speaker therefore waives any copyright and/or performer’s rights and/or any remuneration or indemnity from the organisers and, where applicable, any third party authorized by it. The organisers will have complete freedom in the choice of images and/or voices, editing and possible cuts, in compliance with the exclusions herein contained.

ARTICLE 2

The speaker accepts, in addition to the image and/or voice, the communication of personal data to any partner of the organisers, national or international, involved in the management of the project. According to the regulations concerning the protection of personal data, the organisers are responsible for the processing of personal data used for the purposes of this authorization. The speaker has the right to access, rectify the data and oppose it on legitimate grounds by contacting the Data Protection Officer at the following address: certh@certh.gr and/or valorial@pole-valorial.fr.

..... on the/...../2023

Signatures:

The organisers

The speaker,
preceded by the mention “read and approved”